

**Effects of using the Informed Health
Choices secondary school resources:
protocol for a prospective meta-analysis**

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Colophon

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Abstract

Background: Many people find it difficult to make decisions about what to believe or do regarding “health actions” (things that they can do to care for their health or the health of others). To avoid being misled by unreliable information and to make good choices, people must be able to understand and apply some basic principles (concepts). The Informed Health Choices (IHC) secondary school resources are designed to help students learn and use nine of these concepts. This is a protocol for a prospective meta-analysis of three cluster-randomized trials in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda.

Objective: To estimate the effect of using the IHC secondary school resources in addition to the standard curriculum compared to the standard curriculum in the context where the trial is conducted) on students’ ability to think critically about health actions.

Methods: The participants are lower secondary school students (age 14-16) and their teachers. The intervention is a 2-3-day teacher training workshop, a teachers’ guide, and 10 40-minute lessons taught to the students during a single school term. The comparison is the standard curriculum in each country. The primary outcome measure is the Critical Thinking about Health (CTH) Test. The test is a measure of an individual’s ability to understand and apply the nine key critical thinking concepts included in the lessons. It includes two multiple-choice questions for each concept. The primary outcome is the proportion of students with a passing score on the test. Secondary outcomes include the average score on the test, the proportion of students with a score that indicates mastery of the nine concepts, retention of what the students learned after one year, self-efficacy, intended behaviours, performance on standard, end-of-term examinations, and teachers’ ability to understand and apply the nine concepts measured using the CTH Test. Overall effects will be estimated using inverse variance methods. We will use mixed effects models with individual student data to estimate variation in effects for the primary and first two secondary outcomes in relation to three potential effect modifiers: use of a projector version compared to a blackboard version of the lessons, class size, and student performance on end-of-term examinations prior to the intervention.

Strengths and limitations: Strengths of this meta-analysis are that it is prospective, allowing for collaboration on the design of the trials and certainty that all eligible trials have been included. A limitation is that the review authors are both developing and evaluating the intervention, although there are efforts to minimise bias.

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Background

At the end of the 1990s and the beginning of the 2000s at least 28 frameworks were published describing the need for competencies and curriculum changes for primary and secondary schools in the 21st century.¹ Since then, many countries have moved or are moving from knowledge-based to competence- or skill-based primary and secondary school curricula.² However, there is substantial variation in how “skill”, “competence” or “competency” are defined,^{1,3} which competences are included,² how curriculum changes are being implemented,⁴ and the motivation for changes.^{5,6}

Critical thinking is one of the most often included competences.^{1,2,7} Critical thinking is not a new idea. It dates at least to Socrates over 2400 years ago, and the need to teach critical thinking in school has been argued for over 100 years.^{8,9} There are many different definitions of critical thinking,⁹ and debate about how it should be taught.¹⁰ However, generally, the focus is on dispositions (frequent and voluntary habits of thinking and doing) and abilities that help people to decide what to believe or do. A major new challenge is increased access to information online and in social media, and the need to evaluate that information, much of which is misinformation.⁸

A massive amount of health information can be found online, in addition to information that is disseminated through other channels of communication. This problem has been exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic, which has been accompanied by an “infodemic” – an overload of information including false or misleading information.¹¹ In the context of health, the skills needed to decide what to believe or do are sometimes referred to as critical health literacy.^{12,13} Although both critical thinking and health are widely included in primary and secondary school curricula, critical thinking about health or critical health literacy is not – at least not in Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda, and Norway.¹⁴⁻¹⁷

Many people find it difficult to make decisions about what to believe or do regarding “health actions” (things that they can do to care for their health or the health of others). Being able to understand and apply some basic principles or concepts is essential for using reliable information appropriately and avoiding being misled by unreliable information. This includes concepts about claims, comparisons (research evidence from treatment comparisons), and choices (Table 1). The Informed Health Choices (IHC) Network has developed a list of 49 Key Concepts as a starting point for deciding what to teach.^{18,19} The concepts

provide a basis for developing learning and teaching resources and evaluating learners' ability to think critically about health actions. Most of these concepts are relevant to other types of actions or interventions, including agricultural, educational, and environmental interventions.²⁰

Up to now, few educational interventions to improve people's understanding and use of these concepts have been rigorously evaluated.²¹ To address this gap, we have developed resources to teach some of these concepts in lower-secondary schools. We started by prioritising nine concepts to teach initially (Table 1 and Appendix 1),²² and analysing the context in which the resources will be used in three countries: Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

We developed digital resources using human-centred design – an iterative process of idea generation, prototyping, feedback and observation, and improvements.²³ This was done collaboratively with teachers, students, and curriculum developers in all three countries. The resources are digital to minimise printing and distribution costs. They are designed for use in settings with minimal information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure and unstable internet connectivity and electricity. They are open access and can be used online or offline. Teachers can access and use them with a smartphone or computer, and there are two versions of each lesson: a projector version for classrooms with a projector and a blackboard version for classrooms with only a blackboard, whiteboard, or flipchart.

Randomised trials to evaluate the effects of using the resources in each country will use a common set of outcome measures. The aim of this prospective meta-analysis²⁴ is to synthesize the findings of the three randomized trials of using the resources. Process evaluations are also planned in each country. Those findings will be synthesized in a qualitative evidence synthesis.

The primary question that this review will address is: What are the effects of using the IHC secondary school resources (including teacher training) in addition to the standard curriculum compared to the standard curriculum on the ability of lower secondary school students to think critically about health actions?

Table 1. Key Concepts included in the IHC lower-secondary school resources

Higher level IHC concepts	Included Key Concepts
Claims Claims about effects that are not supported by evidence from fair comparisons are not necessarily wrong, but there is an insufficient basis for believing them.	
Assumptions that treatments* are safe or effective can be misleading.	1. Do not assume that treatments are safe.
	2. Do not assume that treatments have large, dramatic effects.
	3. Do not assume that comparisons are not needed.
Seemingly logical assumptions about re-search can be misleading.	

Higher level IHC concepts	Included Key Concepts
Seemingly logical assumptions about treatments can be misleading.	4. Do not assume that a treatment is better based on how new or technologically impressive it is.
Trust based on the source of a claim alone can be misleading.	5. Do not assume that a treatment is helpful or safe based on how widely used it is or has been.
Comparisons	
To identify treatment effects, studies should make fair comparisons, designed to minimize the risk of systematic errors (biases) and random errors (the play of chance).	
Comparisons of treatments should be fair.	6. Do not assume that personal experiences alone are sufficient.
Reviews of the effects of treatments should be fair.	
Descriptions of effects should clearly reflect the size of the effects .	
Descriptions of effects should reflect the risk of being misled by the play of chance .	7. Consider whether the people being compared were similar.
Choices	
What to do depends on judgements about a problem, the relevance of the available evidence, and the balance of expected benefits, harms, and costs.	
Evidence should be relevant.	
Expected advantages should outweigh expected disadvantages.	8. Be cautious of small studies.
	9. Weigh the benefits and savings against the harms and costs of acting or not.

*We use “treatments”, “health actions”, and “interventions” synonymously. A “treatment” is any intervention (action) intended to improve health, including preventive, therapeutic and rehabilitative interventions, and public health or health system interventions. Because “treatment” is often understood narrowly to only include medical care given to a patient, and “intervention” is not understood by many people, we have used “health action” in the IHC lower-secondary school resources.

Primary objective

The primary objective of this prospective meta-analysis is to estimate the effect of using the IHC secondary school resources – compared to no intervention (the standard curriculum in the context where the trial is conducted) – on the proportion of students with a passing score on the Critical Thinking about Health (CTH) Test (Appendix 2). The test is a measure of an individual’s ability to understand and apply nine Key Concepts (Table 1). It includes two multiple-choice questions for each concept.

Secondary objectives

Secondary objectives are to:

1. estimate the effect of using the IHC secondary school resources compared to no intervention (the standard curriculum in the context where the trial is conducted) on:

- the average score on the CTH Test
 - the proportion of students with a score that indicates mastery of the nine Key Concepts
 - the proportion of students that answer both questions correctly for each key concept
 - retention of what the students learned after one year
 - self-efficacy and intended behaviours
 - academic achievement measured using standard end-of-term examinations
 - use of what was learned in daily life (transfer)
 - adverse effects
 - teachers' ability to understand and apply the nine Key Concepts, measured using the CTH Test
2. estimate variation in effects in relation to possible effect modifiers:
- use of the projector version of the resources
 - class size
 - performance on examinations (academic achievement)

Hypotheses

The hypothesis and rationale for each of the potential effect modifiers is summarised in Table 2. The hypotheses apply to the primary outcome and the first two secondary outcomes. The three potential effect modifiers that we will consider are correlated. We will address this in the analysis by including all of them in a multivariate analysis. In addition, we will explore two other factors measured after the intervention.

Table 2. Rationale for potential effect modifiers

Hypothesis	Rationale
The effects will be larger in schools using the projector version of the resources than in schools using the blackboard version.	The projector version of the resources provides scaffolding (support) for teachers who will be teaching critical thinking about health actions for the first time. The presentations help to ensure that the key messages are clearly communicated and understood by the students, and they include text and illustrations that are not available to students in schools using the blackboard version.
The effects will be larger in schools with a smaller class size	It is easier for teachers to monitor, assess, and engage all the students when there are fewer students in a classroom. In classrooms with a large number of students, some students may not engage, there is less time for individual students to participate in classroom discussions, and it is more difficult for teachers to manage small group discussions.
The effects will be larger for students who perform better on examinations.	We have designed the lessons to benefit all students. Nonetheless, students who perform well on examinations are likely to benefit more than other students. Students who perform well on examinations may be more likely to have higher English proficiency, better study habits,

Hypothesis	Rationale
	better home environments, better cognitive and meta-cognitive skills, and better test-taking skills.
Factors measured after the intervention	
The effects will be larger in schools with higher attendance.	Students who miss lessons are less likely to understand and apply the Key Concepts that are taught in the missed lessons than students who attend the lessons, so effects in schools with better overall attendance across students and lessons are likely to be larger.
The effects will be larger for students with better English reading skills.	English is used in secondary schools in all three countries, but English is not the first language for most students. The resources include explanations of key terms and language that is appropriate for lower-secondary schools. Nonetheless, students with more advanced English reading skills are more likely to comprehend the lessons and the questions in the CTH Test than students with less advanced skills.

Methods

Study design: prospective meta-analysis

The key feature of a prospective meta-analysis is that the studies are identified and determined to be eligible for inclusion in the meta-analysis, and hypotheses and analyses strategies are specified before any results of the studies are known.²⁴ In addition, they facilitate the collection of individual participant data using a standardised set of core outcomes, and collection of data needed to investigate potential effect modifiers.

Three randomized trials that will be included in this meta-analysis were planned collaboratively to ensure a common set of outcome measures and the availability of data to conduct the analyses using individual participant data.²⁵⁻²⁷ Each trial will be conducted in a different country (Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda).

Prospective meta-analyses are like a large multicentre trial.²⁴ Advantages of a prospective meta-analysis are the ability to design, report, and interpret the results of each trial in the context of the country where it will be conducted. As described below, there are important differences between the three countries. At the same time, collaboration on the design of the trials enables investigation of potential effect modifiers in this prospective meta-analysis, as well as estimating overall effects across the three trials.

We have designed the IHC secondary school resources so that they can be translated and adapted to different contexts. However, in the trials, the same resources will be evaluated in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda without translation and with minimal adaptation at the country level.

The three studies share these characteristics, which are the eligibility criteria for this review:

Participants: Students in secondary schools and their teachers

Intervention: Use of the IHC secondary school resources, including a teacher training workshop using teacher training materials included in the resources

Comparison: The standard national curriculum in the country where the trial is conducted, without intervening

Outcomes: Outcomes measured using the CTH Test, including the proportion of students with a passing score (the primary outcome), the average score on the

test, the proportion of students with a score that indicates mastery of the nine concepts, retention of what the students learned after one year, self-efficacy, intended behaviours, and teachers' ability to understand and apply the nine concepts measured using the CTH Test. Additional outcomes include performance on standard, end-of-term examinations, adverse effects, and use of what is learned in daily life (transfer).

Study design: cluster-randomized trials

Search methods

Because we have developed the intervention collaboratively, and it is not yet available to other investigators, it was not necessary to search for other studies that meet the above eligibility criteria. We do not have plans to update this meta-analysis.

Studies and settings

Detailed descriptions of the settings in which the three trials will be conducted can be found in the context analyses undertaken in each country.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Critical thinking about health is not explicitly included in the curriculum and is not being taught in any of the three countries, and there are not resources for teaching critical thinking about health.

Kenya

The Kenyan trial will include a representative sample of the 250 public and private secondary schools in Kisumu County that follow the national curriculum. There are four years of secondary school education in Kenya (following 8 years of primary school), with three school terms each year. Each term normally is 10-13 weeks.

Students normally enrol when they are about 14 years old and graduate when they are about 18. Class size in public secondary schools is generally 40-59 students per class. About 63% of Kisumu secondary schools have at least one laptop or desktop computer, 35% of the schools own a projector, and 17% have Internet access. Students have limited access to computers and few students own phones.

Teachers qualify after undergoing training by an accredited university or training institute. Nearly 95% of secondary school teachers hold a bachelor's degree and about 2% have a post-graduate degree.

The current curriculum is knowledge-based. Teaching is exam-oriented and critical thinking is not assessed in national examinations. Health is a topic in

nine different subjects. The government has plans to develop and implement a new, competency-based curriculum by 2024. “Critical thinking and problem solving” is one of seven core competencies in the framework for the new curriculum. The core competencies cut across subjects. In the proposed curriculum, health education is a subject.

Rwanda

The Rwandan trial will include a representative sample of public, private, and government-aided secondary schools in 10 districts (two from each of the five provinces of Rwanda). There are six years of secondary school in Rwanda (following six years of primary school). The first three years are lower-secondary. There are three school terms each year. Each term is 12-15 weeks.

The official age range is 13-18 for secondary school and 13-15 for lower-secondary. The average number of students per classroom in secondary schools is 39. Most secondary schools have computers (86%) and grid electricity supply (77%). Two thirds have “smart classrooms” that include student computers, a projector, smart boards, and Internet access.

Lower-secondary teachers must have at least a Diploma in Education - a credential earned after two years of post-secondary study that prepares them to teach two subjects. Upper-secondary school teachers must have a four-year bachelor’s degree in education.

A competence-based curriculum was implemented in Rwanda in 2016. All subjects include generic competences for higher order thinking. The generic competences in the curriculum are critical thinking, creativity and innovation, research and problem solving, communication, co-operation, interpersonal relations, life skills, and lifelong learning. Health is a topic in three subjects: biology and health sciences, home science, and English (in which health topics are used as a context for teaching English).

Uganda

The Ugandan trial will include a representative sample of public and private secondary schools that follow the national curriculum in six districts of Uganda (Luwero, Wakiso, Mpigi, Mukono, Kampala, and Kayunga). Secondary education in Uganda is six years (following seven years of primary school). Lower-secondary (“Ordinary Level”) is four years. There are three school terms each year that normally last about 12 weeks.

The entry age of lower-secondary education is 13 years. The average class size is 69. Most schools have at least one computer (87%) and hydroelectric power (71%), 40% have a projector, and most schools do not have Internet access.

Teacher training at National Teachers Colleges requires two years of study. Successful trainees are awarded Diplomas in Secondary Education. Universities also offer undergraduate teaching programs of three to four years in length. The government is currently phasing out teaching diplomas in favour of a bachelor's degree in education.

Uganda's National Curriculum Development Centre introduced a new competence-based curriculum for lower-secondary school students in 2020. Critical thinking is one of seven generic skills in the new curriculum. Several others, such as problem solving, are related to critical thinking. The generic skills are taught across subjects. Health is a topic in biology, physical education, and nutrition and food technology.

Participant characteristics

The three trials are cluster randomized trials in which schools will be randomly allocated to the intervention or a comparison group. The inclusion and exclusion criteria for schools, teachers, and students for each of the trials are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

		Kenya	Rwanda	Uganda
Schools	Inclusion criteria	Public or private schools that follow the national curriculum	Public, private, or government aided schools that follow the national curriculum	Public or private schools that follow the national curriculum
	Exclusion criteria	Schools that participated in the user testing or piloting of the resources, special needs schools, international schools, and schools in districts prone to floods and insecurity	No Internet connection, private schools, schools with less than 100 students or 10 teachers, schools that participated in the user testing and piloting of the resources, and special needs schools, and schools that are hard to reach	Schools that participated in the user testing and piloting of the resources, special needs schools, and adult-only schools

		Kenya	Rwanda	Uganda
Teachers	Inclusion criteria	Form (level) one teachers selected by the principal, with a smartphone or laptop computer, who teach a subject related to health or critical thinking	Level two (senior 2) teachers that teach biology and health sciences, physics, chemistry, or mathematics	Level two (lower secondary level) teachers that teach biology or health sciences
	Exclusion criteria	None	None	None
Students	Inclusion criteria	Form (level) one (year 9) students (normal starting age 14)	Level two (year 8) students (normal starting age 13)	Level two (year 8) students (normal starting age 14)
	Exclusion criteria	Students that choose not to participate	None	None

Intervention characteristics

Characteristics of the intervention are described using the *Guideline for reporting evidence-based practice educational interventions and teaching* (GREET) checklist in Appendix 3.²⁸ The intervention includes a teacher training workshop (Appendix 4) and use of the IHC secondary school resources, in addition to teaching in accordance with the national lower-secondary school curriculum. Schools in the comparison group will continue to teach according to the national lower-secondary school curriculum without intervention.

The resources are called *Be Smart about your Health*. They are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license and are freely available at <https://besmarthealth.org>.

The teacher training workshops will be offered to teachers in the intervention group over 2-3 days prior to the school term during which the IHC lessons will be taught. The workshops will be facilitated by teachers who participated in pilot testing the resources or are in the national teacher network that helped to develop the resources. The facilitators will be provided with 19 presentations and guidance for the workshops, which they will review together with members of the research team prior to the workshop.

The lower-secondary school resources include 10 40-minute lessons, which will be taught over a single school term. The normal school terms in all three countries are 10-13 weeks. Each lesson plan includes an overview, the lesson, and background for teachers. The overviews include learning goals, key terms, teaching strategies, and optional printouts. The lessons include an introduction, an activity, and a wrap-up. There are two versions of each lesson: a blackboard version for teachers using a blackboard, whiteboard, or flipchart; and a

projector version for teachers using a projector. The background sections include a description of what the lesson is about, common misunderstandings, and closely related content that is not included in the lessons because there is not enough time to cover it. In addition, the resources include a teachers' guide and a glossary.

Core outcomes

The CTH Test (Appendix 2) includes 18 multiple-choice questions (MCQs) from the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank, two for each of the Key Concepts included as learning goals in the IHC secondary school resources. We developed the item bank after searching for other appropriate outcome measures to evaluate the IHC primary school resources.²⁹ A systematic mapping review found that studies of educational resources for improving critical thinking about health actions used inconsistent outcome measures.³⁰ We did not find an appropriate outcome measure, and the assessment tools that we found only included a handful of the IHC Key Concepts. Rather than develop an instrument that only included the Key Concepts that were learning goals in the IHC primary school resources, we developed an item bank for all the Key Concepts.

The item bank has been developed based on extensive qualitative and quantitative feedback from methodological experts, health professionals, teachers, and members of the public.³¹ It includes three to four MCQs for each of the 49 IHC Key Concepts. To develop the CTH Test, we started with the 36 MCQs for the nine concepts that are learning goals. To ensure applicability and acceptability of the test, we conducted cognitive interviews with children, adults, and people with methodological expertise in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda. Based on the interviews, we made minor revisions to some of the questions and selected three MCQs for each concept. We then validated the CTH Test using Rasch analysis (Appendix 5). Rasch analysis is a way of developing outcome measurement tools to achieve construct validity. It is a unified approach to address important measurement issues required for validating outcome measures, including internal construct validity (by testing for multidimensionality), invariance of the items (item-person-interaction), and item bias (differential item function).³² For the Rasch analysis, we administered a test that included the 27 MCQs to more than 250 secondary school students and 250 adults in each country. The adults included health professionals, teachers, and other members of the public. Based on the Rasch analysis we selected two MCQs for each Key Concept.

Primary outcome

The primary outcome is the proportion of students with a passing score on the CTH Test (at least 9 correct answers out of 18 MCQs). Students in both the

intervention and comparison schools will take the test at the end of the term when the intervention is delivered - about one week after completion of the last lesson in the intervention schools.

We used a combination of the Nedelsky and Angoff methods to determine an absolute standard (Appendix 6).³³ Both methods rely on expert judges and the concept of individuals who are on the borderline between passing and failing. Using the Nedelsky method, the judges eliminated response options that a borderline student would be able to eliminate. The probability of answering each question correctly is then one divided by the number of remaining response options. Using the Angoff method, the judges then assessed the overall difficulty of each question, taking into consideration the difficulty of the stem (scenario) for the question, the difficulty of the concept, and anything else that might make a question more or less difficult. Nine judges independently estimated the chance of a borderline student answering each MCQ correctly, discussed their judgments, and reached a consensus using a nominal group technique.³⁴ The judges included health researchers and people who teach evidence-informed decision making, educational researchers with experience evaluating interventions to teach critical thinking skills, and curriculum or examination developers. The cut-off for a passing score was then determined by adding-up the consensus probabilities for each of the 18 MCQs.

Secondary outcomes

The following secondary outcomes will be measured in all three trials:

- the average score on the CTH Test
- the proportion of students with a score that indicates mastery of the nine Key Concepts (at least 14 correct answers out of 18 MCQs)

The absolute standard (cut off score) for mastery was determined in the same way as for passing (Appendix 6). But rather than considering individuals on the borderline between passing and failing, the judges considered individuals who are on the borderline between mastering and not mastering the nine Key Concepts.

- the proportion of students that answer both questions correctly for each key concept
- retention of what the students learned after one year

Students in both the intervention and comparison schools will take the CTH Test again one year after they take the test for the first time. The same primary and secondary outcomes will be measured.

- self-efficacy and intended behaviours

Seven questions are included at the end of the CTH Test with Likert response options (Appendix 2). The first four questions assess self-efficacy: how difficult the student thinks it is to:

- know whether a treatment claim is based on research comparing treatments,
- find information about treatments that is based on research,
- know how sure to be about the results of a research study comparing treatments, and
- know if the results of a research study comparing treatments are relevant to them.

The other three questions assess self-reported intended behaviours. The first two of these assess the likelihood that individuals would find out what a claim is based on and whether the claim was based on research. The third asks whether the student would participate in research comparing two treatments.

For these questions, we will dichotomise the responses (e.g., the proportion of ‘very unlikely or unlikely’ responses) in the analysis and we will report the proportions of children for each of the response options.

- academic achievement measured using national examinations

Each trial will collect data on academic achievement for each participating student at three time points: the most recent measure available prior to the school term when the intervention is delivered, the first available measure after that school term, and one year later. Baseline data from the first time will be used as a potential effect modifier. Data from the other two time periods will be used to assess the impact of the intervention on academic achievement. These data, which vary across countries and time points, are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Measures of academic achievement (test performance)

Country	Time period	Data
Kenya	Prior to intervention	Overall score on the national Kenya Certificate of Primary Education (KCPE) exam for math, English, Kiswahili, science, and social studies and religious education

Country	Time period	Data
	After intervention	Overall score on end-of-term examination results for 12/30 subjects examined at the end of the intervention school term. Students choose subjects from five categories: compulsory subjects: English, Kiswahili, math. Science subjects: chemistry, physics, biology. Humanity subjects: geography, history and government, Christian religious, education, Islamic religious education, Hindu religious education. Applied sciences: computer studies, agriculture, home science, art and design, woodwork, metalwork, building construction, power mechanics, electricity, drawing and design, aviation technology. Technical subjects: business studies, French, German, Arabic, Kenya sign language, music
	One year later	Overall score on end-of-term examination results for the 12/30 subjects before the follow up study (see above)
Rwanda	Prior to intervention	Overall score on primary leaving examination for math, science and elementary technology, and English
	After intervention	Overall score on end-of-term examination at the end of the intervention school term for math, physics, chemistry, biology, and English
	One year later	Overall score on lower secondary national examination for math, physics, chemistry, biology, and English
Uganda	Prior to intervention	Overall score on end of term examination for all subjects: mathematics, biology, chemistry, physics, English, history and political education, geography ICT, physical education, and agriculture
	After intervention	Overall score on end of term examination for all subjects: mathematics, biology, chemistry, and physics
	One year later	Overall score on end of term examination for all subjects: mathematics, biology, chemistry, and physics

- teachers' ability to understand and apply the nine Key Concepts, measured using the CTH Test

We will assess the impact of using the IHC secondary school resources on teachers using the CTH Test. Teachers will be asked to take the test at the end of the school term and again after one year, together with their students, and we will measure the same primary outcome (the proportion of teachers with a passing score) and the first two secondary outcomes (the average score and the proportion of teachers with a score that indicates mastery of the nine Key Concepts).

- use of what was learned in daily life (transfer)

If people are unable to “transfer” what they learn in school, the value of a formal education is limited. However, there is uncertainty about how to achieve and evaluate transfer of learning.³⁵ We are developing a model to guide both evaluation and achievement of more distant transfer effects (Appendix 7), particularly application of the concepts to practical decisions about what to believe or do in daily life, as opposed to hypothetical scenarios in the resources or CTH Test. Details of how this outcome will be

assessed will be provided in an update of this protocol. We aim to do this both quantitatively, in the one-year follow-up studies, and qualitatively, in the process evaluations.

- adverse effects

Researchers often overlook potential adverse effects of educational interventions and public health interventions.³⁶⁻³⁸ We are developing a framework to guide efforts to evaluate and prevent of potential adverse effects of using IHC resources (Appendix 7). Each trial will monitor for the potential adverse effects indicated in the framework, as well as any other potential adverse effects.

Teachers will be asked to report any serious adverse events during the trials. However, we will not ask them to monitor for specific events. Serious adverse effects are unlikely, based on findings from the trial of the IHC primary school intervention and process evaluation,^{29,39} and the extensive feedback we have collected from teachers and students in developing and piloting the resources.²³ Asking teachers to monitor for specific adverse effects, some of which they might find difficult to understand or identify (e.g. nihilism or cognitive dissonance), we would risk causing unnecessary confusion and stress, including nocebo effects.

We will report the findings from monitoring for adverse effects in the three trials. Potential adverse effects will also be explored in the process evaluations that will be conducted together with each trial. If potential adverse effects are identified through monitoring and the process evaluations, we will assess those quantitatively in the one-year follow-up study and provide details of how this will be done in an update of this protocol.

Data analysis

The statistician doing these analyses will not be blinded.

For the primary analysis, we will combine the results of the three trials, based on the planned analyses, using inverse variance methods with a random effects model and 95% confidence intervals.⁴⁰ The planned analyses, which are described in the trial protocols and will be reported separately for each trial,²⁵⁻²⁷ will use multi-level logistic and linear regression mixed models, adjusting for the stratification variables used in each of the trials (Table 5).

For the proportion of students with a passing score, and the proportion with a mastery score on the CTH Test, we will pool the log odds ratios. For the average score, we will pool the adjusted mean differences. We will present forest plots for each of these analyses. We will analyse and report results for each key concept, intended behaviours, self-efficacy, academic achievement, and teachers' results on the CTH Test in the same way. We will report the overall effect

estimate, 95% confidence intervals, test for overall effect (p-value) and Tau², Chi², P, and I² for heterogeneity. Dummy tables for presenting the results the primary and secondary outcomes are shown in Appendix 8. Odds ratios will be converted to adjusted differences using average control school proportions across studies.

For the analysis of potential effect modifiers, we will use mixed models with a random effects term for the clusters (schools) and country (trial), fixed effect terms for version of the resources used, class size, and performance on examinations (Table 2), and interaction terms. Because the trials used different stratification variables in the random allocation of schools (Table 5), we will use a common set of fixed effect terms for clusters (schools) across all three trials:

- Location (rural versus non-rural)
- Ownership (public versus private)
- ICT (≥ 1 projector vs no projector, using baseline data for Kenya and Rwanda)
- School performance based on examinations prior to the intervention (Table 4)

Table 5. Stratification variables

Trial	Stratification variables
Kenya	location (rural, urban) and ownership (private, public)
Rwanda	School performance (based on the Rwanda National Examination and School Inspection ranking of schools)
Uganda	Ownership (public, private) and ICT (at least one projector, no projector)

These analyses will be conducted for the primary outcome (the proportion of students with a passing score) and the first two secondary outcomes (the average score and the proportion of students with a score that indicates mastery of the nine Key Concepts). We will use multilevel logistic regression for passing and mastery scores, and multilevel linear regression for average scores on the CTH Test. For the questions that assess applied knowledge or understanding, missing values will be counted as wrong answers.

For this dichotomous, potential effect modifiers (Table 2), we will estimate an odds ratio:

- Schools using the projector version compared to schools using the blackboard version of the resources

For these two continuous, potential effect modifiers (Table 2), we will estimate slopes:

- Class size
- Results (percent correct answers) for the end of the term examinations prior to the intervention (Table 4).

Because reading skills and attendance will be measured after the intervention, we will not report a test of interaction for these variables. For reading skills, we will present the results separately for each subgroup (Table 8 in Appendix 8). English reading skills will be assessed using four questions at the beginning of the CTH Test (Appendix 2): two advanced and two basic questions. We will categorize students' reading skills as "advanced" (all four questions correct), "basic" (both basic questions correct and one or both advanced questions wrong), and "lacking basic" (one or both basic questions wrong). For attendance, we will present graphs showing the relationship between the average attendance for each school across students and lessons (on the x axis) and the effect estimates.

We will follow the guidance of Jakobsen et al. to handle any missing data.⁴¹ Briefly, if complete case data are not available for more than 5% of participants, we will use multiple imputation via chained equations⁴² to impute and analyze 50 complete data sets and will combine estimates using Rubin's rules. We will report and justify any auxiliary variables used for imputation.

Sensitivity analyses will be conducted in the individual trials to explore the risk of bias due to attrition, which may be larger in the control schools than in the intervention schools.²⁹ These will include a weighted analysis using inverse probability weighting, and calculation of upper and lower bounds for the mean difference in test scores using the Lee bounds approach.⁴³ We will summarise the findings of these analyses narratively. Statistical analyses will be performed using Stata version 16 or later (StataCorp LLC, Collage Station, TX, USA).

Sample size and power calculations

Sample size calculations for each trial are based on the primary outcome, the proportion of students with a passing score on the CTH Test (Table 6). Based on the assumptions in Table 6, the meta-analysis will have 99% power to detect a difference of 11.6% for a statistical significance level of 0.05 and 13.3% for a significance level of 0.01 (Table 7).⁴⁴

Table 6. Sample size calculations

Assumptions	Kenya	Rwanda	Uganda	Total
Students per cluster	45	42	69	
Comparison schools	30%	30%	30%	
Detectable difference	20%	20%	20%	
Statistical significance	0.01	0.01	0.01	
Power	90%	90%	90%	
ICC *	0.19	0.19	0.19	
Loss to follow-up †	10%	10%	10%	
Sample size (schools)	80	84	80	244
Students [§]	3,600	3528	5520	12,648

* Intraclass correlation coefficient

† Allowing for a loss to follow-up for schools where it might be impossible to administer the assessment at the end of the term

§ Rough estimate based on the assumed number of students per cluster (school) and the total sample of schools (without any schools lost to follow-up). These figures do not consider individual students (at schools where the test is administered) who do not take the test (e.g., because they are not at school when the test is administered).

Table 7. Power calculations

Statistical significance	Detectable difference		
	99% Power	90% Power	80% Power
0.01	13.6%	10.6%	9.4%
0.05	11.8%	8.9%	7.7%

Data management

The principal investigator for each included trial will be responsible for collecting and managing data and will contribute a complete data set and completed analyses for all the outcomes. Coding of data will be standardized across the three trials. We will collect data centrally for individual schools, students, and teachers. This will include data for each of the outcomes, the planned analyses of potential effect modifiers, and baseline characteristics for the schools, teachers, and students (Table 1 in Appendix 8).

Risk of bias and certainty assessment

The risk of bias will be assessed independently by two researchers who were not involved in the design, implementation, interpretation, or reporting of the three trials or this meta-analysis. They will use the revised Cochrane Collaboration’s tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials to assess the risk of bias in each trial.⁴⁵ They will assess the certainty of the evidence of an important difference for each outcome using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system.^{46, 47}

We will assess the credibility of subgroup differences (potential effect modifiers) using the Instrument to assess the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN).⁴⁸

Ethical considerations

All data that are collected centrally will be de-identified. Procedures for obtaining consent and handling withdrawals are described in each of the trial protocols.

Ethical approval for each trial has been obtained from the relevant authorities in each country:

- the Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology Institutional Ethics Review Committee and the Kenya National Commission of Science and Technology Institute,
- the Rwandan National Ethics Committee,
- the School of Medicine research ethics committee at the Makerere University College of Health Sciences and the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology.

Stakeholder engagement

We will seek feedback on this protocol from researchers who are members of our international advisory group prior to finalising it.

Teachers, students, and other stakeholders have been engaged in the design and evaluation of the intervention.⁴⁹ Teacher networks and student networks have been established in each country to provide input and feedback. Each country also has a national advisory group with key stakeholders, including members of the national curriculum committee or education board and education authorities. Approval for the trials has been obtained from the relevant education authorities in each country. The results and interpretation of the trials and this meta-analysis will be discussed with the networks and advisory groups prior to publication.

Competing interests

The investigators for each trial and this meta-analysis are responsible for both the development and evaluation of the intervention. In addition, we are responsible for the development of the CTH Test. There is a risk of bias from developers of educational interventions who exert a strong influence over the evaluation and have a personal or financial interest in a positive result.⁵⁰ It was not possible for us to commission an independent evaluation, apart from the assessments of the risk of bias and the certainty of the evidence. However, we have no financial interest in a positive result, since all IHC resources are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license. Unrestricted non-commercial use, distribution, and reproduction of the IHC secondary school resources is permitted, provided the source is properly cited. In addition, we will seek guidance from members of our international advisory group regarding perceived bias and ways of mitigating potential bias prior to publication of this protocol and prior to publication of the results of this meta-analysis.

The CTH Test is aligned with the intervention (“treatment-inherent”). That is, the test measures the ability of students to apply the concepts that the resources are designed to teach. Treatment-inherent outcome measures are

associated with larger effect sizes than independent measures.^{10, 29, 51} In addition, critical thinking about health actions will not be taught in the comparison schools. The trials do not compare two ways of teaching critical thinking about health actions. Because of this, it will be inappropriate to compare the effect of our intervention on our outcome measure to the effects of other interventions on independent measures, such as reading or maths tests.

Because there is no other outcome measure suitable for evaluating the IHC secondary school resources,³⁰ we will use an outcome measure developed by us (Appendix 2). However, the included randomized trials will use multiple-choice questions from a database of questions that independent research methodologists judged to have face validity, and end-users have judged to be relevant and acceptable;³¹ we have validated the test using Rasch analyses (Appendix 5); and a group of independent judges have determined the cut-off scores for passing and mastery scores. The multiple-choice questions are designed to require critical thinking on the part of the test-takers and could not be answered by simply repeating content from the resources (Appendix 2). We have been careful to ensure that the examples used in the questions are different from those used in the resources, and that the students will be able to understand the language that was used without having used the resources. Neither the teachers nor the students will be shown the test or similar multiple-choice questions before taking the test.

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Publication policy

Individual datasets remain the property of the trialists in each country and can be published in relevant journals. The overall data for meta-analysis will be held, analysed, and published by the collaborative group. Each of the participating trials will be able to publish their individual trial results prior to or concurrent with publication of the final prospective-meta-analysis results.

Availability of data and other materials

The data are available through an agreement between the principal investigators of the included trials. The trialists remain the custodians of their own data. The de-identified data for the individual trials and code for the meta-analysis

will be made publicly available via a GitHub repository and will be archived in Zenodo when the results are published. The IHC secondary school resources are available online at <https://besmarthealth.org/>.

Protocol registration

This protocol was registered with PROSPERO May 31, 2022, ID 336580. The individual trials will be registered in Pan African Clinical Trial Registry (Table 9).

Table 9. Trial identifiers

Trial	Trial identifier	Date registered
Kenya	PACTR202204883917313	5 April 2022
Rwanda	PACTR202203880375077	15 February 2022
Uganda	PACTR202204861458660	14 April 2022

Protocol amendments

All protocol amendments will be numbered sequentially, dated, and recorded in Prospero.

Authors' contributions

ADO prepared the first draft of this protocol. MM, FC, and RS prepared first drafts of the protocols for the three included randomized trials and subsequent revisions. CJR provided statistical expertise. All the authors read, provided feedback, and approved the final manuscript. ADO is the guarantor.

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Appendices

1. Prioritisation of Informed Health Choices Key Concepts
2. Critical Thinking about Health (CTH) Test
3. Teacher training workshop
4. Development and validation of the CTH Test
5. Determination of cut-offs for passing and mastery scores
6. Framework for preventing and evaluating potential adverse effects
7. Dummy tables
8. PRISMA-P 2015 Checklist

References

1. Erstad O, Voogt J. The twenty-first century curriculum: issues and challenges. In: Voogt J, Knezek G, Christensen R, Lai K-W, editors. *Second Handbook of Information Technology in Primary and Secondary Education*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing; 2018. p. 19-36.
<https://www.duo.uio.no/handle/10852/71882>
2. Care E, Anderson K, Kim H. *Visualizing the breadth of skills movement across education systems*. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution; 2016.
<http://hdl.voced.edu.au/10707/440516>
3. Tahirsylaj A, Sundberg D. The unfinished business of defining competences for 21st century curricula—a systematic research review. *Curric Perspect*. 2020;40(2):131-45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41297-020-00112-6>
4. Nsengimana T, Rugema Mugabo L, Hiroaki O, Nkundabakura P. Reflection on science competence-based curriculum implementation in Sub-Saharan African countries. *Int J Sci Educ B*. 2020;1-14.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21548455.2020.1778210>
5. Anderson-Levitt K. Global flows of competence-based approaches in primary and secondary education. *Cah Rech Éduc Savoires*. 2017(16):47-72.
<https://journals.openedition.org/cres/3010>
6. Anderson-Levitt K, Gardinier MP. Introduction contextualising global flows of competency-based education: polysemy, hybridity and silences. *Comp Educ*. 2021;57(1):1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2020.1852719>
7. Voogt J, Roblin NP. A comparative analysis of international frameworks for 21st century competences: Implications for national curriculum policies. *J Curric Stud*. 2012;44(3):299-321. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2012.668938>
8. Larson L, Forzani E, Leu DJ. *New Literacies: Curricular Implications*. In: Voogt J, Knezek G, Christensen R, Lai K-W, editors. *Second Handbook of Information Technology in Primary and Secondary Education*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing; 2018. p. 19-36.
<https://www.duo.uio.no/handle/10852/71882>
9. Geng F. A content analysis of the definition of critical thinking. *Asian Soc Sci*. 2014;10(19):124. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ass.v10n19p124>
10. Abrami PC, Bernard RM, Borokhovski E, Waddington DI, Wade CA, Persson T. Strategies for teaching students to think critically: a meta-analysis. *Rev Educ Res*. 2015;85(2):275-314. <https://doi.org/10.3102%2F0034654314551063>
11. Pian W, Chi J, Ma F. The causes, impacts and countermeasures of COVID-19 "Infodemic": A systematic review using narrative synthesis. *Inf Process Manag*. 2021;58(6):102713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102713>

12. Chinn D. Critical health literacy: a review and critical analysis. *Soc Sci Med*. 2011;73(1):60-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.04.004>
13. Sykes S, Wills J, Rowlands G, Popple K. Understanding critical health literacy: a concept analysis. *BMC Public Health*. 2013;13:150. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-150>
14. Chesire F, Ochieng M, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, Oxman M, Nsangi A, et al. Contextualizing critical thinking about health using digital technology in secondary schools in Kenya: a qualitative analysis. *Res Square*. preprint 29 March 2022. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1345080/v1>
15. Mugisha M, Uwitonze AM, Chesire F, Senyonga R, Oxman M, Nsangi A, et al. Teaching critical thinking about health using digital technology in lower secondary schools in Rwanda: A qualitative context analysis. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(3):e0248773. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248773>
16. Ssenyonga R, Sewankambo NK, Mugagga SK, Nakyejwe E, Chesire F, Mugisha M, et al. Learning to think critically about health using digital technology in Ugandan lower secondary schools: a contextual analysis. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(2):e0260367. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0260367>
17. Lund HM, Mathisen PE, Rekkavik ME, Voll E. Teaching critical thinking about health claims: market analysis for Norwegian primary and lower secondary school. *Zenodo*. 2018. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748281>
18. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. *F1000Res*. 2019;7:1784. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.16771.2>
19. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. Version 2019. IHC Working Paper. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4746689>
20. Aronson JK, Barends E, Boruch R, Brennan M, Chalmers I, Chislett J, et al. Key concepts for making informed choices. *Nature*. 2019;572(7769):303-6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-02407-9>
21. Cusack L, Del Mar CB, Chalmers I, Gibson E, Hoffmann TC. Educational interventions to improve people's understanding of key concepts in assessing the effects of health interventions: a systematic review. *Syst Rev*. 2018;7(1):68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-018-0719-4>
22. Agaba JJ, Chesire F, Mugisha M, Nandi P, Njue J, Nsangi A, et al. Prioritisation of Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts to be included in lower-secondary school resources: a consensus study. *medRxiv*. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.04.11.22273708>
23. Rosenbaum S, Oxman M, Oxman AD, Chelagat F, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, et al. Human-centred design development of Informed Health Choices (IHC) learning resources for secondary school students: protocol. IHC Working Paper. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748445>
24. Seidler AL, Hunter KE, Cheyne S, Ghersi D, Berlin JA, Askie L. A guide to prospective meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 2019;367:l5342. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l5342>

25. Chesire F, Kaseje M, Ochieng M, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, Oxman M, et al. Effect of the Informed Health Choices secondary school intervention on the ability of lower secondary students in Kenya to think critically about health information and choices: Protocol for a cluster-randomized trial. IHC Working Paper. 2022. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562940>
26. Mugisha M, Nyirazinyoye L, Simbi CMC, Chesire F, Ssenyonga R, Oxman M, et al. Effects of Informed Health Choices secondary school resources on the ability of Rwandan students to think critically about health: protocol for a cluster-randomised trial. IHC Working Paper. 2022. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562788>
27. Ssenyonga R, Oxman AD, Nakyejwe E, Mugagga SK, Nsangi A, Semakula D, et al. Does the use of the Informed Health Choices secondary school resources improve critical thinking about the effects of health among secondary school students in Uganda? A cluster-randomised trial protocol. IHC Working Paper. 2022. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6560218>
28. Phillips AC, Lewis LK, McEvoy MP, Galipeau J, Glasziou P, Moher D, et al. Development and validation of the guideline for reporting evidence-based practice educational interventions and teaching (GREET). *BMC Med Educ.* 2016;16:237. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-016-0759-1>
29. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Oxman M, Rosenbaum S, et al. Effects of the Informed Health Choices primary school intervention on the ability of children in Uganda to assess the reliability of claims about treatment effects: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2017;390(10092):374-88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(17\)31226-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(17)31226-6)
30. Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Nsangi A, Semakula D. Interventions and assessment tools addressing key concepts people need to know to appraise claims about treatment effects: a systematic mapping review. *Syst Rev.* 2016;5(1):215. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0389-z>
31. Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Semakula D, Nsangi A, Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Rosenbaum S, et al. Measuring ability to assess claims about treatment effects: the development of the 'Claim Evaluation Tools'. *BMJ Open.* 2017;7(5):e013184. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013184>
32. Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Guttersrud O, Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Group IHC. Measuring ability to assess claims about treatment effects: a latent trait analysis of items from the 'Claim Evaluation Tools' database using Rasch modelling. *BMJ Open.* 2017;7(5):e013185. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013185>
33. Livingston SA, Zieky MJ. Passing scores: A manual for setting standards of performance on educational and occupational tests. Princeton, NJ: Educational Testing Service; 1982. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED227113>
34. Jones J, Hunter D. Consensus methods for medical and health services research. *BMJ.* 1995;311(7001):376-80. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.311.7001.376>
35. Barnett SM, Ceci SJ. When and where do we apply what we learn?: A taxonomy for far transfer. *Psychol Bull.* 2002;128(4):612. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.128.4.612>
36. Zhao Y. What works may hurt: Side effects in education. *J Educ Change.* 2017;18(1):1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-016-9294-4>

37. Bonell C, Jamal F, Melendez-Torres GJ, Cummins S. 'Dark logic': theorising the harmful consequences of public health interventions. *J Epidemiol Community Health*. 2015;69(1):95-8. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2014-204671>
38. Lorenc T, Oliver K. Adverse effects of public health interventions: a conceptual framework. *J Epidemiol Community Health*. 2014;68(3):288-90. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2013-203118>
39. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Glenton C, Lewin S, Oxman AD, Oxman M, et al. Informed health choices intervention to teach primary school children in low-income countries to assess claims about treatment effects: process evaluation. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9(9):e030787. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-030787>
40. Deeks J, Higgins J. Statistical algorithms in Review Manager 5. In: Higgins J, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page M, et al., editors. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 62* (updated February 2021): Cochrane; 2021. <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/statistical-methods-revman5>
41. Jakobsen JC, Gluud C, Wetterslev J, Winkel P. When and how should multiple imputation be used for handling missing data in randomised clinical trials - a practical guide with flowcharts. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2017;17(1):162. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0442-1>
42. van Buuren S. Multiple imputation of discrete and continuous data by fully conditional specification. *Stat Methods Med Res*. 2007;16(3):219-42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0962280206074463>
43. Lee DS. Training, wages, and sample selection: Estimating sharp bounds on treatment effects. *Rev Econ Stud*. 2009;76(3):1071-102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-937X.2009.00536.x>
44. University of Aberdeen Health Services Research Unit. Cluster sample size calculator user manual. Aberdeen: University of Aberdeen; 1999. <https://dokumen.tips/documents/cluster-sample-size-calculator-user-manual-sample-size-calculator-user-manual-health.html>
45. Sterne JAC, Savović J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Blencowe NS, Boutron I, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*. 2019;366:l4898. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l4898>
46. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, Kunz R, Vist G, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction-GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):383-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.04.026>
47. Zeng L, Brignardello-Petersen R, Hultcrantz M, Siemieniuk RAC, Santesso N, Traversy G, et al. GRADE guidelines 32: GRADE offers guidance on choosing targets of GRADE certainty of evidence ratings. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021;137:163-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.03.026>
48. Schandelmaier S, Briel M, Varadhan R, Schmid CH, Devasenapathy N, Hayward RA, et al. Development of the Instrument to assess the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN) in randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses. *CMAJ*. 2020;192(32):E901-e6. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.200077>
49. Nsangi A, Oxman AD, Oxman M, Rosenbaum SE, Semakula D, Ssenyonga R, et al. Protocol for assessing stakeholder engagement in the development and evaluation

of the Informed Health Choices resources teaching secondary school students to think critically about health claims and choices. PLoS One. 2020;15(10):e0239985.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239985>

50. Edovald T, Nevill C. Working out what works: The case of the Education Endowment Foundation in England. ECNU Rev Educ. 2021;4(1):46-64.
<https://doi.org/10.1177%2F2096531120913039>

51. Slavin R, Madden NA. Measures inherent to treatments in program effectiveness reviews. J Res Educ Effect. 2011;4(4):370-80.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2011.558986>

Appendices

1. Prioritisation of Informed Health Choices Key Concepts

Background

The Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts are principles for thinking critically about healthcare claims and deciding what to do.¹ The Key Concepts provide a framework for designing curricula, learning and teaching resources, and evaluation tools.

Objective

To prioritise which of the 49 IHC Key Concepts to include in IHC resources for lower-secondary schools in East Africa.

Methods

We used an iterative, structured consensus process built on Wiggins' and McTighe's "backward design" approach,² the Nominal Group Technique consensus process,³ and Feinstein's criteria for sensibility.⁴ Ten judges from Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda prioritised the IHC Key Concepts to be included in the IHC secondary school resources. Three were curriculum specialists or teachers, one was a health promotion officer, and the other six were health researchers who were members of the project team and were familiar with the IHC Key Concepts. Before independently assessing the 49 concepts (Table A1.1),⁵ they agreed on the central ideas underlying what students should learn, the core tasks that students should be able to perform, and six criteria that were used:

- How important is the concept for understanding the central ideas?
- How important is the concept for enabling students to perform the core tasks?
- Will students be able to understand the concept?
- Is the concept frequently not understood or considered?
- What is the potential impact of not understanding or considering the concept?
- Are students likely to be able to apply the concept in their daily lives?

After they reached a consensus, we collected informal feedback from teacher and student networks and advisory groups in each country, from our international advisory group, and from other members of our research team.⁶

A second panel assessed the concepts prioritized by the first panel using the same six criteria, after being provided with a summary of the feedback. The second panel included nine judges, seven of whom were members of the first panel. Two were curriculum specialists, one was a teacher, one was an education researcher, and the other five were members of the project team. Three other curriculum specialists participated in the discussions but did not complete independent assessments of the concepts.

Results

The first panel prioritized 29 of the 49 concepts (Table A1.1). After reviewing feedback on the first consensus, the second panel assessed 27 concepts and prioritised 17 of those. The original plan was to develop two sets of resources to be used during two school terms. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic and school closures, it was only possible to produce one set of resources for a single school term. After collecting feedback on prototypes of the resources, the second consensus panel agreed on the nine concepts included in the IHC secondary school resources.

Table A1.1. Prioritised IHC concepts

IHC Key Concepts		Consensus			
		1	2a	2b	Final
1	Claims				
1.1	It should not be assumed that treatments are safe or effective - or that they are not.				
1.1a	Treatments can cause harms as well as benefits.	✓	✓	✓	✓
1.1b	Large, dramatic effects are rare.	✓	✓	✓	✓
1.1c	It is rarely possible to be certain about the effects of treatments.	✓	✓		
1.2	Seemingly logical assumptions are not a sufficient basis for claims.				
1.2a	Treatment may not be needed.	✓	✓		
1.2b	Beliefs alone about how treatments work are not reliable predictors of the presence or size of effects.	✓	✓	✓	
1.2c	Assumptions that fair comparisons of treatments in research are not applicable in practice can be misleading.				
1.2d	An outcome may be associated with a treatment but not caused by it.	✓	✓	✓	
1.2e	More data is not necessarily better data.				
1.2f	Identifying effects of treatments depends on making comparisons.	✓	✓	✓	✓
1.2g	The results of one study considered in isolation can be misleading.	✓	✓		
1.2h	Widely used treatments or those that have been used for decades are not necessarily beneficial or safe.	✓	✓	✓	✓
1.2i	Treatments that are new or technologically impressive may not be better than available alternatives.	✓	✓	✓	✓
1.2j	Increasing the amount of a treatment does not necessarily increase its benefits and may cause harm.	✓	✓	✓	
1.2k	Earlier detection of 'disease' is not necessarily better.				

IHC Key Concepts	Consensus			
	1	2a	2b	Final
1.2l It is rarely possible to know in advance who will benefit, who will not, and who will be harmed by using a treatment.				
1.3 Trust in a source alone is not a sufficient basis for believing a claim.				
1.3a Your existing beliefs may be wrong.	✓	✓	✓	
1.3b Competing interests may result in misleading claims.	✓	✓	✓	
1.3c Personal experiences or anecdotes alone are an unreliable basis for most claims.	✓	✓	✓	✓
1.3d Opinions alone are not a reliable basis for claims.	✓	✓	✓	
1.3e Peer review and publication by a journal do not guarantee that comparisons have been fair.				
2 Comparison				
2.1 Comparisons of treatments should be fair.				
2.1a Comparison groups should be as similar as possible.	✓	✓	✓	✓
2.1b Indirect comparisons of treatments across different studies can be misleading.				
2.1c The people being compared should be cared for similarly apart from the treatments being studied.	✓	✓	✓	
2.1d If possible, people should not know which of the treatments being compared they are receiving.	✓			
2.1e Outcomes should be assessed in the same way in all the groups being compared.	✓	✓	✓	
2.1f Outcomes should be assessed using methods that have been shown to be reliable.				
2.1g It is important to assess outcomes in all (or nearly all) the people in a study.				
2.1h People's outcomes should be counted in the group to which they were allocated.				
2.2 Syntheses of studies need to be reliable.				
2.2a Reviews of studies comparing treatments should use systematic methods.				
2.2b Failure to consider unpublished results of fair comparisons may result in estimates of effects that are misleading.				
2.2c Treatment claims based on models may be sensitive to underlying assumptions.				
2.3 Descriptions should clearly reflect the size of effects and the risk of being misled by the play of chance.				
2.3a Verbal descriptions of the size of effects alone can be misleading.	✓	✓		
2.3b Relative effects of treatments alone can be misleading.	✓	✓		
2.3c Average differences between treatments can be misleading.	✓			
2.3d Small studies may be misleading.	✓	✓		✓
2.3e Results for a selected group of people within a study can be misleading.				
2.3f The use of p-values may be misleading; confidence intervals are more informative.				
2.3g Deeming results to be "statistically significant" or "non-significant" can be misleading.				
2.3h Lack of evidence of a difference is not the same as evidence of "no difference".				

IHC Key Concepts	Consensus			
	1	2a	2b	Final
3 Choices				
3.1 Problems and options should be clear.				
3.1a Be clear about what the problem or goal is and what the options are.	✓	✓	✓	
3.2 Evidence should be relevant.				
3.2a Attention should focus on all important effects of treatments, and not surrogate outcomes.				
3.2b Fair comparisons of treatments in animals or highly selected groups of people may not be relevant.	✓	✓		
3.2c The treatments compared should be similar to those of interest.				
3.2d There should not be important differences between the circumstances in which the treatments were compared and those of interest.				
3.3 Expected advantages should outweigh expected disadvantages.				
3.3a Weigh the benefits and savings against the harms and costs of acting or not.	✓	✓	✓	✓
3.3b Consider the baseline risk or the severity of the symptoms when estimating the size of expected effects.	✓	✓		
3.3c Consider how important each advantage and disadvantage is when weighing the pros and cons.	✓	✓		
3.3d Consider how certain you can be about each advantage and disadvantage.	✓	✓		
3.3e Important uncertainties about the effects of treatments should be addressed in further fair comparisons.				
Number of concepts	29	27	17	9

* ✓ = Included

1 = First consensus

2a = Concepts assessed by the second consensus panel. Two concepts prioritised by the first panel (2.1d and 2.3c) were not considered after feedback from teachers, students, curriculum developers, and other members of the research team.

2b = Concepts prioritised by the second consensus panel

Final = Prioritised concepts after collecting feedback on prototypes of the resources and agreed on by the second consensus panel. One concept that was not initially prioritised by the second consensus panel (2.3d) was included as one of the nine IHC Key Concepts included in the secondary school resources.

References

1. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. *F1000Res.* 2019;7:1784. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.16771.2>
2. Wiggins GP, Wiggins G, McTighe J. *Understanding by Design.* Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development; 2005.
3. Jones J, Hunter D. Consensus methods for medical and health services research. *BMJ.* 1995;311(7001):376-80. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.311.7001.376>

4. Feinstein A. The theory and evaluation of sensibility. *Clinimetrics*. New Haven: Yale University Press; 1987. p. 141-66.
5. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. Version 2019. IHC Working Paper. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4746689>
6. Nsangi A, Oxman AD, Oxman M, Rosenbaum SE, Semakula D, Ssenyonga R, et al. Protocol for assessing stakeholder engagement in the development and evaluation of the Informed Health Choices resources teaching secondary school students to think critically about health claims and choices. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(10):e0239985.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239985>

2. Critical Thinking about Health Test

The Critical Thinking about Health Test

Instructions

Before you start, please note that some words in this questionnaire may not be familiar to you. Please read through the following explanations:

A **TREATMENT** is anything done to care for yourself, so you stay well or, if you are sick or injured, so you get better and not worse. For example, skin cream.

A **TREATMENT CLAIM** is something someone says about whether a treatment causes something to happen or to change. A claim can be true or can be false. For example, if a friend says “Using skin cream will help your skin rash”.

A **RESEARCH STUDY** is a way to answer a question by carefully collecting information. For example, a study might be done to answer the question: Does skin cream help people with skin rash?

RESULTS of a study are what the study found. For example, whether people who use skin cream had less skin rash.

When something happens by **CHANCE**, it is not possible to tell in advance what will happen. For example, if you flip a coin, you cannot tell in advance if it will land on one side or the other side.

This test was developed for use at the end of the *Be Smart About Your Health* lessons in Uganda, Kenya and Rwanda. The questions included in this test were taken from the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank (read more about the item bank here (<https://www.informedhealthchoices.org/claim-evaluation-tools/>)).

First, read the text above the questions and then answer each question on **the SCORE sheet**, using one of the provided answers.

For each question, choose what you think is the best answer and **fill in the circle** for that answer in the score sheet, like this.

If you want to change your answer, carefully erase the first circle that you filled in.

Do not fill in more than one circle for each question.

The examples below show you the one correct way and some wrong ways to mark your answers.

Be sure to fill in the circles the correct way.

Part 1.
Questions about you

1.1 Your school code

1.2 Your teacher code

1.3 Your gender

Female

Male

1.4 Your age

Part 2. Reading ability questions

A doctor did a research study to find out if drinking tea keeps people from getting sick. He flipped a coin to decide who should get the tea and who should not. People who got tea went to the doctor's office every day to drink their tea. At the end of the study, people who got the tea were less likely to be sick than those who got no tea.

Based on the text above, please answer the following questions:

2.1 Who went to the doctor's office every day?

Options:

- A) People who did not get tea
- B) People who got tea
- C) Everyone
- D) People who got sick

2.2 How did the doctor decide who should get tea?

Options:

- A) By flipping a coin
- B) By asking people if they would like tea
- C) The doctor gave tea to those who were more likely to be sick
- D) The doctor asked people who came to his office

A doctor did a research study to find out if drinking tea keeps people from getting sick. He flipped a coin to decide who should get the tea and who should not. People who got tea went to the doctor's office every day to drink their tea. At the end of the study, people who got the tea were less likely to be sick than those who got no tea.

Based on the text above, please answer the following questions:

2.3 What was the treatment?

Options:

- A)** Tea
- B)** Sleep
- C)** The study
- D)** The doctor

2.4 What was the result of the study?

Options:

- A)** Drinking tea can help people from getting sick
- B)** Doctors should toss coins when doing studies
- C)** People should go to the doctor if they are sick
- D)** Not drinking tea can help people from getting sick

Part 3.

Questions about claims

3.1

Anne has pain in her ear, and she asks her brother, Hassan, what to do about it. He says that once, when he had a pain like that, he cleaned his ear with hot water. The next day, his ear pain was gone. Based on his experience, he says rinsing with hot water is helpful for ear pain.

Question: **Do you agree with Hassan?**

Options:

- A)** Yes. Because this is Hassan's experience, it is likely to be true
- B)** No, Hassan's experience is not enough to be sure
- C)** Yes, Hassan rinsed his ear with hot water and the next day his ear pain was gone

3.2

Sarah says that medicines from well-known companies, costing more money, are not necessarily the best. Medicines from less known companies, costing less money, may be just as good or even better.

Question: **Is Sarah right?**

Options:

- A)** No, medicines costing less money are more likely to be harmful than expensive medicines
- B)** Yes, just because the medicine is expensive does not mean that it will work better than other medicines
- C)** No, expensive medicines made by well-known companies are better than less expensive medicines made by lesser-known companies

3.3

Edith has stomach pain. Edith's mother says that fruit juice is a good treatment for stomach pain. She learnt about this treatment from Edith's grandmother. Over many years, other families she knows have also used fruit juice to treat stomach pain.

Question: Based on this, how sure can we be that fruit juice is a good treatment for stomach pain?

Options:

- A)** Not very sure. Even though people have used fruit juice over many years, that does not mean that it helps stomach pain
- B)** Very sure. If it has worked for Edith's mother and other people who have tried it, it will probably work for her too
- C)** Not very sure. Edith should ask more families if they use fruit juice to treat stomach pain

3.4

John has a skin rash on his leg. A shop sells several skin creams to treat skin rashes. John chooses a skin cream from a well-known company, even though it is more expensive than the other creams. John thinks this skin cream is more likely to heal his rash than the other skin creams because it is more expensive.

Question: **Is John right?**

Options:

- A)** No, just because the skin cream is expensive does not mean that it will work better than other creams
- B)** It is not possible to say. However, expensive skin creams are likely to be better because the companies spend more time making them
- C)** No, the skin cream is probably not as good as the other skin creams. People just like well-known companies more

3.5

Sarah has a sickness. There is a medicine for it, but she is not sure if she should try it. A research study comparing the medicine with no medicine found that the medicine was helpful but also that it could be harmful. Three of Sarah's friends are telling her what to do.

Question: Which of the following things said by her friends is more correct?

Options:

- A) She should only take the medicine if many people have tried the medicine before
- B) She should only take the medicine if she thinks it will help her more than it will harm her
- C) If Sarah has enough money to buy the medicine, it could not hurt to try it

3.6

Imagine you and your friends have formed a team to take part in a local running competition. People on the other teams all had bananas for breakfast. You and your friends did not have bananas for breakfast and lost the race. Some people say that this was because your team had bread for breakfast and that made them run slower.

Question: If you did a research study comparing people who eat bananas for breakfast with people who don't eat bananas for breakfast, how would you decide who should have bananas for breakfast?

Options:

- A)** By chance (like flipping a coin) to make sure the two groups are as similar as possible
- B)** By having the teams decide, to make it as fair as possible
- C)** By having the teachers decide, because they know who would benefit best from eating bananas

3.7

Regina has a sickness that makes it difficult for her to breathe. She hears on the radio about a medicine that has helped many people with breathing problems.

Question: How sure can Regina be that the medicine does not have any harms?

Options:

- A)** It is not possible to say, it depends on how much hope Regina has in the medicine
- B)** Very sure, since the medicine has helped many people, it is unlikely that it also harms people
- C)** Not very sure, because all medicines may harm people as well as help them

3.8

Outside the city where Paul lives there are many farms. The farmers often get coughs. For many years, the farmers have used strong tea to treat their coughs. They say that the tea is good for them and that it protects them from becoming more sick.

Paul says that the farmers may not be right, and that the strong tea may not help coughs.

Question: **Do you agree with Paul?**

Options:

- A)** Yes, Paul should try drinking strong tea himself to know for sure. The strong tea may work differently on him
- B)** Yes, we can only know for sure if the strong tea works if it has been compared with other treatments in studies
- C)** No, the farmers would not have used strong tea for all those years if it did not work

3.9

Jane often has headaches. Her doctor tells her that there is a medicine that may help her, but it may harm her. The medicine is also very expensive.

Question: What does Jane need to think about before using the medicine?

Options:

- A)** If the medicine will help her more than it will hurt her, and if she thinks it is worth paying so much money for it
- B)** If anybody she knows has tried the medicine so that she can ask them what they thought about it
- C)** If she should ask another doctor, since the doctor must be wrong. A medicine which is helpful cannot be harmful

3.10

Mercy wanted to know if eating bananas makes you run faster. To find out, she invited her six best friends to take part in a research study. Three friends each got bananas, and three friends did not get bananas. At the end of the study, the friends who did not get bananas ran a lot faster.

Question: **How sure can Mercy be about her study's results?**

Options:

- A)** More sure, because Mercy found a difference between the groups in how fast they ran. This means that the study included enough people.
- B)** Less sure, because the difference between the two groups could have occurred by chance
- C)** More sure, if she repeats the study with six more friends

3.11

Doctors studied people with stomach pain before and after they took a new medicine. After taking the new medicine, many people felt less pain.

Question: Can we be sure that the new medicine is good for treating stomach pain?

Options:

- A)** No, taking the new medicine should have been compared either with not taking the medicine, or with taking an older medicine
- B)** Yes, people were asked how much pain they felt before and after they took the new medicine
- C)** Yes, the study was done by doctors

3.12

A new and an old mosquito spray (insecticide) were compared in a research study. In the study, two houses were sprayed with the new spray, and two houses were sprayed with the old spray. Based on this study, the new spray was better for protecting against mosquito bites than the old spray. Neither of the sprays was found to be harmful to people.

Question: **How sure can you be about what the study found?**

Options:

- A)** Less sure, because only four houses were studied and the differences between sprays may have happened by chance
- B)** More sure, because the new spray was better for protecting against mosquito bites and it was not harmful
- C)** More sure, because the new spray was found to be better, and the differences between sprays is unlikely to have happened by chance

3.13

On the radio, there is someone selling a treatment - a new juice. The seller says that if you drink one glass of it every day, you will not get sick.

Question: How sure can you be that the new juice will keep you from getting sick?

Options:

- A)** It is not possible to say. I would have to try the new juice myself to be sure
- B)** Very sure, otherwise this news would not be on the radio
- C)** Not very sure. Very few treatments work so well

3.14

Dr. Javier has done a research study giving a new medicine to people who were vomiting. Some of the people stopped vomiting after they got the new medicine. Dr. Javier says that this means that the medicine works.

Question: **Is Dr. Javier right?**

Options:

- A)** No. The people who used the medicine were not compared with similar people who did not use the medicine
- B)** Yes, some of the people stopped vomiting
- C)** No, since not all the people stopped vomiting

3.15

George has stomach pain. The last time George had a stomach pain was two months ago. That time, he drank some hot milk and after an hour, his stomach pain was gone. Therefore, George says hot milk cures stomach pain.

Question: **Is George right?**

Options:

- A)** It is not possible to say. His stomach pain might have gone away without the hot milk
- B)** It is not possible to say, but it is likely to be true based on the fact that George had this experience
- C)** Yes, George's experience is enough to show that hot milk makes stomach pain go away

3.16

Esther recommends a new treatment – a medicine - for pain. She says that everyone who has tried it felt better.

Question: How sure can you be that what Esther says about the new medicine is true?

Options:

- A)** Not very sure. Very large benefits, where everyone or nearly everyone gets better because of a treatment are rare
- B)** It is not possible to say. To be sure I would have to try the medicine for myself
- C)** Very sure. The medicine must be very good since everyone who has tried it got better

3.17

A doctor wanted to know which of two treatments was best for headaches. In a study to find out, he asked people to choose which treatment they would like to get. He compared the people who took each of the two treatments.

Question: How sure can we be about the results of this comparison of the two treatments?

Options:

- A) More sure, because the doctor asked people to choose which treatment they wanted
- B) Less sure, because the doctor should have decided who got which treatment
- C) Less sure, because the doctor should have given people one of the two treatments by chance (like flipping a coin)

3.18

Mary wanted to find out which plants were best for treating people with headaches, so she did a research study to compare green plants with yellow plants. The people who used the green plants had fewer headaches compared to the people who used the yellow plants.

Question: How sure can we be that green plants are better than yellow plants?

Options:

- A)** It is not possible to say. Mary did not study possible harms of the plants
- B)** Very sure, since people who used the green plants had fewer headaches
- C)** Not very sure, it depends on how much people believe the green plants will work

Part 4. Questions about your views

Below are some questions about what you think. **There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.**

Below are some actions. Please read each one carefully and give the answer that comes closest to how difficult or easy you find each of the actions to be. There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.

4.1 Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing if a claim about a treatment is based on a research study comparing treatments?

Options:

- A) Very difficult
- B) Difficult
- C) Easy
- D) Very easy
- E) I don't know

4.2 Question: How difficult or easy do you think it is to find information about treatments that is based on research studies comparing treatments?

Options:

- A) Very difficult
- B) Difficult
- C) Easy
- D) Very easy
- E) I don't know

Below are some actions. Please read each one carefully and give the answer that comes closest to how difficult or easy you find each of the actions to be. There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.

4.3 Question: How difficult or easy do you find judging the trustworthiness of the results of a research study comparing treatments?

Options:

- A) Very difficult
- B) Difficult
- C) Easy
- D) Very easy
- E) I don't know

4.4 Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing if the results of a research study comparing treatments are relevant to you?

Options:

- A) Very difficult
- B) Difficult
- C) Easy
- D) Very easy
- E) I don't know

Think about a sickness that you might get. Imagine someone claiming (saying) that a treatment might help you get better.

4.5 Question: How likely are you to find out what the claim was based on (for example by asking the person making the claim)?

Options:

- A) Very unlikely
- B) Unlikely
- C) Likely
- D) Very likely
- E) I don't know

4.6 Question: How likely are you to find out if the claim was based on a research study comparing the treatment to no treatment?

Options:

- A) Very unlikely
- B) Unlikely
- C) Likely
- D) Very likely
- E) I don't know

4.7. Question: How likely are you to say "yes" if you are asked to participate in a research study comparing two treatments for your sickness?

Options:

- A) Very unlikely
- B) Unlikely
- C) Likely
- D) Very likely
- E) I don't know

Part 5.

Questions about your experience with the Be Smart about Your Health lessons

Below are some questions about what you think. **There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.**

5.1. Question: How much did you like or dislike the lessons?

Options:

- A) I liked the lessons very much
- B) I liked the lessons a little
- C) I disliked the lessons a little
- D) I disliked the lessons very much

5.2. Question: How easy or difficult were these lessons to understand?

Options:

- A) Very difficult to understand
- B) Difficult to understand
- C) Easy to understand
- D) Very easy to understand

5.3. Question: How helpful or unhelpful has what you have learned been to you?

Options:

- A) Very helpful to me
- B) Helpful to me
- C) Unhelpful to me
- D) Very unhelpful to me

3. Guideline for reporting evidence-based practice educational interventions and teaching (GREET) checklist¹

BRIEF NAME

1. Intervention: Informed Health Choices (IHC) secondary school resources

The intervention, use of the IHC secondary school resources will be compared to routine practice (teaching according to the national lower-secondary school curriculum without intervening).

WHY this educational process

2. Theory: The IHC secondary school resources are based on the *IHC Key Concepts* framework. The framework includes concepts (principles) that people should understand and apply when deciding whether to believe a claim about the effects of health actions (things that people do to care for their health or the health of others) and what to do.^{2, 3} The framework is based on evidence of the importance of the included concepts,⁴ logic, feedback, other relevant frameworks,⁵ and adaptation of the IHC Key Concepts to other types of interventions such as educational, environmental, and policing interventions.⁶

The resources were developed by the investigators between 2020 and 2022 using human-centred design methods.⁷ This includes cycles of idea generation and prototyping, piloting with observation, user-testing with teachers and students, and feedback from teachers, students, and curriculum developers in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda, and an international advisory group. The aim of the design process was to ensure that teachers and students find the resources to be engaging, useful, and easy to use.

The teaching strategies used in the resources are based in part on an overview of systematic reviews of teaching strategies,⁸ and draw on several educational theories. These include social constructivist theory (which postulates that learning can be maximized through well-designed, intentional social interaction with other learners),⁹ the theory of active student response (which postulates that learning is enhanced by high levels of active student response),¹⁰ and

the elaborative retrieval hypothesis (which postulates that the search for correct answers on practice tests or quizzes results in multiple retrieval routes which aid later recall).¹¹

3. Learning objectives: The primary learning goal is for students to have a basic ability to think critically about health actions and understand why this is important. They should be able to recognise claims about the effects of health actions and assess some of those claims. They should understand why it is important for them that researchers study the effects of health actions and recognise two key features of reliable comparisons of health actions. They should recognise that health actions can have both advantages and disadvantages and the importance of weighing the benefits and savings against the harms and costs when deciding what to do.

4. Evidence-based practice content: The resources focus on nine IHC Key Concepts that were prioritised by curriculum developers, teachers, and researchers in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda (Appendix 1).

WHAT

5. Materials: The IHC secondary school resources (*Be smart about your health*) are open access digital resources for lower-secondary school teachers. The 10 lessons are provided as lesson plans in two formats: for teachers who are using either a blackboard and or a projector in the classroom. The aim is for students to learn to think critically about health claims and choices. The resources will be made available to schools in the intervention group. Teachers in those schools will download the resources to a computer or smartphone and deliver the lessons. Schools in both the control and intervention group will continue teaching the national curriculum, which does not include teaching critical thinking about health. No additional materials will be provided to the control schools.

Each Lesson includes an introduction, an activity, and a wrap-up. The introduction includes the key messages from the previous lesson, a question about the previous lesson, and what this lesson is about. The activity is designed to help students achieve the learning goals. The wrap-up includes a question about what was learned, the key messages for the lesson, a homework assignment, if there is one, and what the next lesson is about. Lessons 5 and 10 include quizzes and discussions of application of what students learned in their daily lives.

For each of the 10 lessons there is an overview and background for teachers. The overview includes learning goals, key terms introduced in the lesson, and the main teaching strategies used in the lesson. The background includes a description of what the lesson is about and if relevant, common misunderstandings and closely related content that is not covered in the lesson.

In addition, there is a teachers' guide, materials for teacher training workshops, information about how to use the resources (help), optional printouts (PDFs) for teachers and students, and a glossary. Teachers will be provided with binders with printouts at the training workshops.

6. Educational strategies: Key strategies used across lessons include guided note taking, small group discussion, use of response cards,¹⁰ homework, use of a standard lesson structure, setting objectives and providing feedback, and multimedia design. Other strategies used in some of the lessons include concept cartoons, inquiry-based instruction, and role play.

7. Incentives: The incentive for teachers and students is the value they perceive in learning to think critically about health actions. Teachers at schools without Internet access will be reimbursed for the cost of downloading the resources and any other costs related to participation in the trial. They will not be paid for participating in the trial and there will be no other financial incentives for the schools, head teachers, teachers, or students. The evaluation administered at the end of the school term will not count towards the students' school marks or assessment of the teachers or schools.

WHO WILL PROVIDE

8. Instructors: The head teacher at each participating school will select teachers of relevant subjects (e.g., biology) for year-1 or year-2 of lower-secondary school. The teachers will be invited to a 2-3-day workshop to introduce them to the resources and the learning content. The training will be facilitated by other teachers who have participated in one of the teaching networks that helped to develop the resources or who piloted use of the resources (Appendix 3). The facilitators will be provided with presentations and other materials for the workshops, and they will review the material and plans for the workshops with the research team prior to the workshops.

HOW

9. Delivery: The 10 lessons will be delivered by the teachers during regular classroom time or, if necessary, outside of regular classroom time. They can use a computer, smartphone, or printouts when delivering the lessons. Depending on what equipment is available to the teachers, they will deliver the lessons to students using only a blackboard or using a projector and slide presentations that are included in the digital resources. The number of students in a class will vary.

WHERE

10. Environment: Representative samples of schools will be recruited, including rural and urban schools. The conditions in the schools will vary. Details of the contexts in each of the three countries can be found in reports of the context analyses undertaken prior to developing the resources.¹²⁻¹⁴

WHEN and HOW MUCH

11. **Schedule:** The 10 lessons will be taught in a single school term. Each school will decide how to fit the lessons into the schedule for that term.

12. **Amount of time:** Each lesson is designed to be delivered in a single period (40 minutes). The students will be encouraged to collect and assess claims about the effects of health actions outside of class and to discuss claims with their families and friends. The teacher will need up to 30 minutes to prepare for each lesson.

PLANNED CHANGES

13. **Adaptation:** No specific adaptation is required, but teachers will be able to adapt the lessons, for example by using different or additional examples or editing the presentations.

UNPLANNED CHANGES

14. **Modifications:** As part of planned process evaluations, teachers will be asked to complete an evaluation form after each lesson, including information about changes they made to the lesson plan, and each teacher will be observed for one lesson. We will not give feedback to the teachers during the trial.

HOW WELL

15. **Attendance:** The teacher will record attendance for each lesson. Students will be encouraged to attend all lessons by telling them when the next lesson will be and its learning goals. The lessons have been designed to appeal to students and to make clear the relevance and importance of the learning goals.

16. **Fidelity:** We will explore the extent to which the lessons were delivered as planned in the process evaluation, based on the evaluation forms completed by teachers after each lesson, our observations of their teaching a lesson, and interviews with teachers and students.

17. **Delivery schedule:** The teachers will be asked to record when each lesson was taught, the duration of each lesson, and whether all the lesson were completed as planned.

References

1. Phillips AC, Lewis LK, McEvoy MP, Galipeau J, Glasziou P, Moher D, et al. Development and validation of the guideline for reporting evidence-based practice educational interventions and teaching (GREET). *BMC Med Educ.* 2016;16:237. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-016-0759-1>

2. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. *F1000Res*. 2019;7:1784. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.16771.2>
3. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. Version 2019. IHC Working Paper. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4746689>
4. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for Informed Health Choices: a framework for enabling people to think critically about health claims. Version 2022. IHC Working Paper. 2022.
5. Oxman AD, Martinez Garcia L. Comparison of the Informed Health Choices Key Concepts to other frameworks that are relevant to learning how to think critically about treatment claims, comparisons, and choices: protocol for a mapping review. 2018. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4765543>
6. Aronson JK, Barends E, Boruch R, Brennan M, Chalmers I, Chislett J, et al. Key concepts for making informed choices. *Nature*. 2019;572(7769):303-6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-02407-9>
7. Rosenbaum S, Oxman M, Oxman AD, Chelagat F, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, et al. Human-centred design development of Informed Health Choices (IHC) learning resources for secondary school students: protocol. IHC Working Paper. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748445>
8. Oxman AD, Dahlgren A, Garcia Marti S, Kaseje M, Nsangi A, Rosenbaum S, et al. The effects of teaching strategies on learning to think critically in primary and secondary schools: protocol for an overview of systematic reviews. IHC Working Paper. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748398>
9. Igel C. Cooperative learning. Denver, CO: McREL International; 2010. <https://www.mcrel.org/classroom-instruction-that-works-research-report/>
10. Randolph JJ. Meta-analysis of the research on response cards: effects on test achievement, quiz achievement, participation, and off-task behavior. *J Posit Behav Interv*. 2007;9(2):113-28. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F10983007070090020201>
11. Pan SC, Rickard TC. Transfer of test-enhanced learning: meta-analytic review and synthesis. *Psychol Bull*. 2018;144(7):710-56. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/bul0000151>
12. Chesire F, Ochieng M, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, Oxman M, Nsangi A, et al. Contextualizing critical thinking about health using digital technology in secondary schools in Kenya: a qualitative analysis. *Res Square*. preprint 29 March 2022. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1345080/v1>
13. Mugisha M, Uwitonze AM, Chesire F, Senyonga R, Oxman M, Nsangi A, et al. Teaching critical thinking about health using digital technology in lower secondary schools in Rwanda: A qualitative context analysis. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(3):e0248773. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248773>
14. Ssenyonga R, Sewankambo NK, Mugagga SK, Nakyejwe E, Chesire F, Mugisha M, et al. Learning to think critically about health using digital technology in Ugandan lower secondary schools: a contextual analysis. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(2):e0260367. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0260367>

4. Teacher training workshop

The teacher training workshops will be facilitated by teachers who participated in the pilot study or are members of the teachers' network. They will use resources provided in the IHC secondary school resources, including the schedule below, [the presentations](#) listed in the schedule, a [Teachers' guide](#), and [printouts](#) that will be provided in a workshop binder. Members of the research team will provide the facilitators with the workshop materials and review the materials with them. This approach to teacher training is like the approach normally used in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda to introduce changes to the curriculum.

Teacher training workshop schedule and facilitator notes

Notes for facilitators

- Adjust the suggested times as needed, depending on when the workshop will start and end each day, how many days the workshop will last, and how much time you feel you need for each session.
- Send the agenda to participants in advance and instructions to access the BeSmartHealth website before the workshop, so that the resources are installed on their computer or smartphone.
- Make sure everyone brings a computer or smartphone that they have used to access the BeSmartHealth website before the workshop. They should, if possible, open all the lessons (so that they are downloaded, in case of problems with the Internet at the workshop). Teachers who plan on using the projector version of the lessons should download the slides, if possible, since those are not automatically saved.
- Hand out workbooks at the workshop.
- Review all the presentations before the workshop.
- Download the presentations as PowerPoint files, in case of a poor Internet connection.
- For the sessions on each lesson, do some in the plenary / large group (e.g., Lesson 1) and others in small groups. When relevant, model teaching lessons or teaching strategies that are more difficult.
- Make sure that participants have time to review and discuss each lesson. The presentations are intended as introductions and should not take up the entire session. They should be shortened, if necessary, to allow more time for the teachers to review and discuss the lessons – assuming there is an adequate Internet connection, or the teachers have opened/downloaded the lessons prior to the workshop.
- If it is feasible/practical to have a 3-day workshop, you could give participants more time to prepare for teaching the lessons, e.g., make the sessions that focus on each of the 10 lessons longer.

Time	Minutes	Presentations	Notes for facilitators
Day 1			
08:00	30	1. Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitators introduce themselves Ask participants to introduce themselves in breakout groups and when they say something
	30	2. Overview of the lessons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slides 23-25: Unless you think teachers might be interested in the curriculum in other countries, you can delete or skip the two slides that are not for your country
	60	3. Introduction to the learning resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 2 has an embedded link to a 3-minute video. However, to show the video, your computer must be connected to a speaker, and you need a good Internet connection. To open the video in a downloaded PowerPoint file, click on the image. Give the participants time to explore the resources when you get to Slide 8 Suggest that they look at each of the things listed on the slide <ul style="list-style-type: none"> You might want to demonstrate each of those things by opening and projecting besmarthealth.org You might want to have them explore besmarthealth.org in pairs or small groups and to help each other Tell the participants they can ask for help if they have any problems
	30	Break	
10:30	45	4. Teaching strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 8 is a demonstration of buzz groups. Give participants about 2 minutes to discuss. Get feedback (responses to the questions) from some of the participants. You can let them know that when you go through the individual lessons, you will use small groups Slide 10 is a demonstration of class discussion. The idea is for the participants to answer the questions, not for the facilitator to answer them. If participants ask questions, try asking the participants what they think, rather than answering the question yourself Slides 13-15 are a demonstration of using response cards. Give the participants feedback, since they should not be able to see each other's responses, and allow time for discussion, e.g., ask what they like or do not like about using response cards
	45	5. Teaching tips	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 14: Give the participants time to try using the resources offline and to download a presentation and/or a PDF file
	60	Lunch	
13:00	40	6. Lesson 1	
	40	7. Lesson 2	
	40	8. Lesson 3	
	30	Break	
15:30	40	9. Lesson 4	

Time	Minutes	Presentations	Notes for facilitators
	40	10. Lesson 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You might want to move this session to day 2 and have the participants start planning for the term at the end of day 1 (see presentation 16. Preparing for the term) and then come back to planning for the term again, after the session on Lesson 10.
16:40	20	Wrap-up for the day (no presentation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ask if there are any questions Give information about dinner and start time tomorrow Encourage them to read the background for each of the lessons
Day 2			
08:00	40	11. Lesson 6	
	40	12. Lesson 7	
	40	13. Lesson 8	
	30	Break	
10:30	40	14. Lesson 9	
	40	15. Lesson 10	
	40	16. Preparing for the term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 5: Give the participants time to start filling in a schedule for the term Tell them to continue preparing for teaching the lessons if they don't need the time to work on their schedule
	60	Lunch	
13:30	60	17. Other relevant resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 12: Give participants time to explore the resources
	40	18. Development and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The research fellows may want to do this presentation, since it is not about teacher training, and is primarily about the randomised trial Slide 14: Give them time to fill in a teacher evaluation form. Add screen shots and link to the form to the presentation Add slides for baseline data collection, if you plan on collecting that during the workshop
	20	19. Wrap-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give them time to finish preparing for the lessons if there is time at the end of the day Prepare a workshop evaluation form, add a slide with a screenshot and link, and have teachers complete it
15:30	30	Break	

5. Development and evaluation of the Critical Thinking about Health Test

Background

The Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts are principles for evaluating the trustworthiness of treatment claims and comparisons, and for making informed choices.¹ The Claim Evaluation Tools item bank contains multiple-choice questions (MCQs) that assess an individual's understanding of and ability to apply the IHC Key Concepts.² The item bank includes four MCQs for each IHC Key Concept. We developed the databank after finding that existing measurement tools only included a handful of the Key Concepts.³

In a previous study, we developed a measurement instrument that included 26 MCQs, two each for 13 Key Concepts. We used Rasch analysis to validate that instrument, which was used in a randomized trials of a primary school intervention (that included 12 of the concepts) and a podcast for parents (that included 9 of the concepts).⁴⁻⁶

Objective

To develop and evaluate an outcome measure for randomized trials of a secondary school intervention that includes nine concepts, using MCQs from the Claim Evaluation Tools item bank.

Methods

We first conducted cognitive interviews and piloted the questionnaire to get feedback from secondary school students in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda on the acceptability and relevance of the terminology and formats used in the questionnaire. We then recruited secondary school students and adults in the three countries to complete the questionnaire for a Rasch analysis. We estimated that recruiting approximately 500 people in each country, with an equal distribution of men and women and secondary school students and adults would be adequate.

Rasch analysis is a dynamic way of developing outcome measures to achieve construct validity.⁷ It addresses important measurement issues required for validating an outcome measure, including; internal construct validity (by testing for multidimensionality), invariance of the items (item-person-interaction), and item bias (differential item function). We explored summary and individual fit to the Rasch model using the RUMM2030 software.

The questionnaire used for the Rasch analysis included two item-sets, the first evaluated the ability to apply the IHC Key Concepts using MCQs (scored dichotomously). It included three MCQs for each of the nine Key Concepts. Each MCQ had three response options (Appendix 2). The other item-set evaluated intended behaviour and self-efficacy (Appendix 2). Data were collected primarily electronically using a service hosted by the University of Oslo (Nettskjema). For participants that did not have Internet access, we used paper questionnaires with answer sheets that could be scanned using ZipGrade.

Findings

Findings from the cognitive interviews and piloting of the questionnaire led to only minor changes, such as changing some of the names and other terminology used in the MCQs to improve familiarity. We also changed the format of the intended behaviours and self-efficacy questions.

We recruited 1671 participants who completed the questionnaires. Overall, both item-sets were found to have good fit to the Rasch model. They showed good targeting and were reliable (Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7). Individual person fit to the ability item set was very good, and most items showed good fit to the Rasch model. However, this analysis gave good indication of potential items that should be removed because of high fit residuals, under-discrimination, or DIF.

Individual item fit for the intended behaviour and self-efficacy questions was satisfactory, but analysis of individual personal fit suggested that some people in our target audience may not respond as expected to those questions. Three items measuring intended behaviour had disordered item curves. A reanalysis of these indicated that dichotomizing the intended behaviour and self-efficacy items would resolve this issue.

There was no local dependency in either of the item-sets, and both item-sets were found to have acceptable unidimensionality.

Based on the findings of the Rasch analysis we selected two MCQs for each Key Concept for the Critical Thinking about Health (CTH) Test.

Conclusion

The two item-sets were found to be reliable with satisfactory measurement properties. We used the findings of the cognitive interviews and the Rasch analysis to refine and improve the outcome measure and ensure the validity and reliability of the CTH Test.

References

1. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Informed Health Choices Group. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices. *F1000Res*. 2019;7:1784. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.16771.2>

2. Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Semakula D, Nsangi A, Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Rosenbaum S, et al. Measuring ability to assess claims about treatment effects: the development of the 'Claim Evaluation Tools'. *BMJ Open*. 2017;7(5):e013184. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013184>
3. Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Nsangi A, Semakula D. Interventions and assessment tools addressing key concepts people need to know to appraise claims about treatment effects: a systematic mapping review. *Syst Rev*. 2016;5(1):215. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0389-z>
4. Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Guttersrud O, Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Group IHC. Measuring ability to assess claims about treatment effects: a latent trait analysis of items from the 'Claim Evaluation Tools' database using Rasch modelling. *BMJ Open*. 2017;7(5):e013185. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013185>
5. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Oxman M, Rosenbaum S, et al. Effects of the Informed Health Choices primary school intervention on the ability of children in Uganda to assess the reliability of claims about treatment effects: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2017;390(10092):374-88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(17\)31226-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(17)31226-6)
6. Semakula D, Nsangi A, Oxman AD, Oxman M, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Rosenbaum S, et al. Effects of the Informed Health Choices podcast on the ability of parents of primary school children in Uganda to assess claims about treatment effects: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2017;390(10092):389-98. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(17\)31225-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(17)31225-4)
7. Tennant A, Conaghan PG. The Rasch measurement model in rheumatology: what is it and why use it? When should it be applied, and what should one look for in a Rasch paper? *Arthritis Rheum*. 2007;57(8):1358-62. <https://doi.org/10.1002/art.23108>

6. Determination of cut-offs for passing and mastery scores

Background

The Critical Thinking about Health (CTH) Test includes two multiple-choice questions (MCQs) for each of the nine IHC Key Concepts included in the IHC secondary school resources. There are three response options for each question.

Objective

To determine cut-off scores for passing (having at least a borderline ability to apply the Key Concepts) and mastery (being at least on the border of having mastered the concepts).

Methods

Eight people judged the likelihood that someone on the border between passing and not passing, and someone on the border between having mastered and not having mastered the concepts would answer each MCQ correctly. The judges included two curriculum specialists (from Kenya and Rwanda), three secondary school teachers (from Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda), three health service researchers (from Croatia, Norway, and Uganda). They determined cut-off scores by summing up the probability of answering each MCQ correctly. They were provided with persona describing borderline students, the correct answers, the difficulty of each question based on the Rasch analysis that was conducted to validate the test (Appendix 5), and instructions based on a combination of two widely used methods: Nedelsky's and Angoff's.^{1,2}

The Nedelsky method allows judges to eliminate response options that a borderline learner would be able to eliminate. The chances of getting each question correct is then equal to one divided by the number of remaining response options, for example, if there are two remaining response options (one of which is the correct option), the chances of a borderline individual answering the question correct is $\frac{1}{2}$ or 50%. The resulting cut-off score is then determined by adding up the probabilities for all the questions. With Angoff's method, which is one of the most widely used, the judges assess the difficulty of each question as a whole.

Using a combination of Nedelsky and Angoff's methods, the judges started with the Nedelsky method, then increased or decreased the assigned probability for each question based on an

overall assessment. This gave the judges a logical approach to making an initial judgement about the difficulty of each question. It then allowed them to adjust for uncertainty about the number of response options a borderline individual would eliminate, the difficulty of the stem (scenario) for the question, the difficulty of the concept, anything else that might make a question more or less difficult, and the difficulty of the question based on the Rasch analysis.

The judges answered the 18 questions without looking at the answers to get a sense of the difficulty of the questions. They discussed the instructions, undertook a practice round of assessing some of the MCQs, and then discussed their judgements and agreed on guidance for assessing the MCQs. They then independently assessed all 18 MCQs. Their assessments were summarised and discussed before reaching a consensus on the cut-off scores using a nominal group technique.

Results

The consensus judgements varied from 40 to 55% for the percentage of students on the border between passing and not passing who would answer each question correctly. They varied from 60% to 85% for students on the border between having mastered and not having mastered the concepts. The judges agreed that 9 out of 18 questions needed to be answered correctly to pass and 14 out of 18 questions needed to be answered correctly to demonstrate mastery.

Conclusion

Although there was wide variation in many of the individual judgements, it was possible to reach a consensus on the cut-off scores for passing and mastery in an online meeting that lasted less than 90 minutes.

References

1. Livingston SA, Zieky MJ. Passing scores: A manual for setting standards of performance on educational and occupational tests. Princeton, NJ: Educational Testing Service; 1982. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED227113>
2. Angoff WH. Scales, Norms, and Equivalent Scores. Princeton, NJ: Educational Testing Service; 1984. https://www.ets.org/research/policy_research_reports/publications/book/1984/ibmt
3. Jones J, Hunter D. Consensus methods for medical and health services research. *BMJ*. 1995;311(7001):376-80. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.311.7001.376>

7. Evaluating “far transfer” of learning and potential harms

Evaluating “far transfer” of learning

If people are unable to “transfer” what they learn in school to other contexts, the value of a formal education is limited.¹ As follows, if students are unable to transfer skills that they learn from the IHC secondary school intervention, the value of the intervention is limited. The more different the transfer context is from the learning context, the “further” the transfer. There is often uncertainty about how best to evaluate far transfer.¹

The primary outcome measure for the trial—the multiple-choice items from the Claim Evaluation Tools bank—is a measure of near transfer. In other words, applying the nine IHC Key Concepts within the context of the intervention (the learning context) is similar overall to applying them to the Claim Evaluation Tools items (the transfer context), although there are important differences. For example, in both contexts, students are intended to apply the concepts to hypothetical scenarios, as opposed to practical decisions. On the other hand, in the context of the intervention, students are intended to apply the concepts together, guided by their teachers, while in the context of the assessment, they are intended to apply them independently.

In a separate study, parallel to the preparation and publication of this protocol, we are developing a model (Figure 1) to identify possible intermediate and far transfer effects of our intervention, such as application of concepts to practical decisions. Based on the model, we will determine methods and develop measures for evaluating those effects qualitatively in process evaluations and quantitatively when we measure outcomes after one year.

Figure 1. Model for achieving and evaluating transfer of learning from the IHC secondary school intervention

1. Explicitly explained in the intervention
2. Implicitly explained in the intervention
3. At least 13 fields: agriculture, economics, education, environmental management, international development, informal learning, management, nutrition, planetary health, policing, speech and language therapy, social welfare, and veterinary medicine framework²
4. Hypothetical scenarios
5. Practical decisions about what to believe or do

Evaluating potential harms

Researchers and others often overlook potential adverse effects of educational interventions,³ and public health interventions.^{4,5} In another separate study, we are developing a framework of potential adverse effects of the IHC secondary school intervention, informed by expert and stakeholder feedback, including input from teachers familiar with the project. Based on the framework, we will determine methods and develop measures for evaluating any potential adverse effects. The categories of adverse effects in the framework are described in Table 1. Table 2 shows the undesirable outcomes in each category.

Table 1. Categories of potential adverse effects

Category	Description
<i>Decision-making harms</i>	Behaviours and beliefs that contribute to poor choices
<i>Psychological harms</i>	Uncomfortable thoughts and feelings
<i>Equity harms</i>	Inequities in the distribution or size of effects
<i>Group and social harms</i>	Harmful interactions between individuals, groups, and systems
<i>Waste</i>	Waste of time and resources
<i>Unknown</i>	None of the above

Table 2. Potential undesirable outcomes.

Category	Undesirable outcome¹
<i>Decision-making harms</i>	Incorrect or unnecessary application of learning
	Misunderstanding
	Overconfidence
	Inappropriate distrust ²
<i>Psychological harms</i>	Cynicism or pessimism ³
	Uncomfortable cognitive dissonance
	Work/schoolwork-related stress
<i>Equity harms</i>	Benefit-based inequity
	Harm-based inequity
<i>Group and social harms</i>	Conflict
<i>Waste</i>	Wasted time or resources
<i>Any</i>	Other

1. The adverse effect is an increase in the given outcome.

2. Distrust might also be a psychological harm.

3. Cynicism or pessimism might also be a decision-making harm.

Monitoring for potential harms

Serious adverse effects of the IHC secondary school intervention are unlikely based on results of the trial of the IHC primary school intervention and process evaluation.^{6,7} Moreover, we have taken steps to prevent potential adverse effects of the secondary school intervention, informed by 1) findings and experiences from the development⁸ and evaluation of the primary school resources; 2) findings from piloting and user-testing prototypes of the secondary school resources, as part of the human-centred design approach;⁹ and 3) early versions of the framework of potential adverse effects, including theoretical mechanisms. For example, in the secondary school resources, we explicitly address limitations of the intervention, such as the limited number of IHC Key Concepts covered. Acknowledging this limitation is intended to prevent users from becoming overconfident in their ability to make informed choices.

Nonetheless, in the lessons that we observe during the trial, we will monitor for adverse outcomes, including those specified in the framework, and we will ask teachers to

report any adverse outcomes to the primary investigator. We will not ask teachers to monitor for specific adverse outcomes, which again are unlikely, especially within the study period, and might also be difficult for teachers to understand and identify. This is to avoid nocebo effects and unnecessary confusion or stress. If a teacher asks for an example of an adverse outcome, we will provide as many as necessary, starting with those in the framework that are relatively likely during the study period, and relatively easy to understand and identify, such as conflict.

References

1. Barnett SM, Ceci SJ. When and where do we apply what we learn?: A taxonomy for far transfer. *Psychol Bull.* 2002;128(4):612. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.128.4.612>
2. Aronson JK, Barends E, Boruch R, Brennan M, Chalmers I, Chislett J, et al. Key concepts for making informed choices. *Nature.* 2019;572(7769):303-6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-02407-9>
3. Zhao Y. What works may hurt: Side effects in education. *J Educ Change.* 2017;18(1):1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-016-9294-4>
4. Lorenc T, Oliver K. Adverse effects of public health interventions: a conceptual framework. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2014;68(3):288-90. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2013-203118>
5. Bonell C, Jamal F, Melendez-Torres GJ, Cummins S. 'Dark logic': theorising the harmful consequences of public health interventions. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2015;69(1):95-8. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2014-204671>
6. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Oxman M, Rosenbaum S, et al. Effects of the Informed Health Choices primary school intervention on the ability of children in Uganda to assess the reliability of claims about treatment effects: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2017;390(10092):374-88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(17\)31226-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(17)31226-6)
7. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Glenton C, Lewin S, Oxman AD, Oxman M, et al. Informed health choices intervention to teach primary school children in low-income countries to assess claims about treatment effects: process evaluation. *BMJ Open.* 2019;9(9):e030787. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-030787>
8. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Rosenbaum SE, Oxman AD, Oxman M, Morelli A, et al. Development of the informed health choices resources in four countries to teach primary school children to assess claims about treatment effects: a qualitative study employing a user-centred approach. *Pilot Feasibility Stud.* 2020;6:18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40814-020-00565-6>
9. Rosenbaum S, Oxman M, Oxman AD, Chelagat F, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, et al. Human-centred design development of Informed Health Choices (IHC) learning resources for secondary school students: protocol. *IHC Working Paper.* 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748445>

8. Dummy tables

Table 1: Characteristics of the participants

		Control schools	Intervention schools
Schools		N=	N=
Country	Kenya	n (%)	n (%)
	Rwanda	n (%)	n (%)
	Uganda	n (%)	n (%)
Location	Rural	n (%)	n (%)
	Semi-urban	n (%)	n (%)
	Urban	n (%)	n (%)
Ownership	Public	n (%)	n (%)
	Private	n (%)	n (%)
Teachers		N=	N=
Completed tests		n (%)	n (%)
Country	Kenya	n (%)	n (%)
	Rwanda	n (%)	n (%)
	Uganda	n (%)	n (%)
Education	Certificate or diploma	n (%)	n (%)
	University degree	n (%)	n (%)
Experience (years)	Median (IQR)	n (n to n)	n (n to n)
	(Range)	(n to n)	(n to n)
Main subject taught	Science	n (%)	n (%)
	Other	n (%)	n (%)
Sex	Women	n (%)	n (%)

		Control schools	Intervention schools
Students (enrolled at start of term)		N=	N=
Completed tests*		n (%)	n (%)
Country	Kenya	n (%)	n (%)
	Rwanda	n (%)	n (%)
	Uganda	n (%)	n (%)
Completed tests per class [§]	Median (IQR)	n (n to n)	n (n to n)
	(Range)	(n to n)	(n to n)
Sex	Girls	n (%)	n (%)
Age	Median (IQR)	n (n to n)	n (n to n)
	(Range)	(n to n)	(n to n)

Table 2: Main results - test scores

	Control schools N schools = N children =	Intervention schools N schools = N children =	Adjusted difference	Odds ratio*	ICC
Primary outcome					
Mean score, %	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean difference: % (95% CI % to %)		n
Passing score (≥ n out of 18 correct answers)	% of children (N=)	% of children (N=)	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Secondary outcomes					
Mean score, %	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean difference: % (95% CI % to %)		n
Mastery score (≥ n out of 18 correct answers)	% of children (N=)	% of children (N=)	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Teachers' scores					
	N teachers =	N teachers =			
Mean score, %	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean difference: % (95% CI % to %)		
Passing score (≥ n out of 18 correct answers)	% of teachers (N=)	% of teachers (N=)	% more teachers (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	
Mastery score (≥ n out of 18 correct answers)	% of teachers (N=)	% of teachers (N=)	% more teachers (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	

Table 3: Intended behaviours

Think about an illness that you might get. Imagine someone claiming (saying) that a particular treatment might help you get better.

	How likely are you to find out what the claim was based on (for example by asking the person making the claim)?		How likely are you to find out if the claim was based on a research study comparing the treatment to no treatment (a fair comparison)?		How likely are you to say “yes” if you are asked to participate in a research study comparing two treatments for your illness (a fair comparison)?	
	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=
Missing	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
I don't know	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Very unlikely	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Unlikely	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Likely	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Very likely	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Likely or very likely*	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Odds ratio	n (95% CI n to n)		n (95% CI n to n)		n (95% CI n to n)	
Adjusted Difference	% (95% CI % to %)		% (95% CI % to %)		% (95% CI % to %)	

* Missing values and don't know will be pooled with unlikely and very unlikely.

Table 4: Self-efficacy

How difficult or easy would you find each of these actions to be?

	Assessing whether a claim about a treatment is based on a research study comparing treatments (a fair comparison)		Assessing where I can find information about treatments that is based on research studies comparing treatments (fair comparisons)		Assessing how sure I can be about the results of a research study comparing treatments (the trustworthiness of the results)		Assessing if the results of a research study comparing treatments are likely to be relevant to me	
	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=	Control schools N=	Intervention schools N=
Missing	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
I don't know	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Very difficult	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Difficult	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Easy	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Very easy	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Easy or very easy*	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Odds ratio	n (95% CI n to n)		n (95% CI n to n)		n (95% CI n to n)		n (95% CI n to n)	
Adjusted difference	% (95% CI % to %)		% (95% CI % to %)		% (95% CI % to %)		% (95% CI % to %)	

* Missing values and don't know will be pooled with difficult and very difficult.

Table 5: Academic achievement

	Control schools N schools = N children =	Intervention schools N schools = N children =	Adjusted difference
Mean score, %	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean difference: % (95% CI % to %)

Table 6: Intervention school student's views of the lessons

How much did you like what you learned in these lessons?		How helpful to you is what you learned in these lessons?		How easy or difficult to understand did you find these?		Do you trust what you learned in these lessons?	
Intervention schools N=							
Missing	n (%)	Missing	n (%)	Missing	n (%)	Missing	n (%)
Dislike a lot	n (%)	Very unhelpful	n (%)	Very difficult	n (%)	Very little trust	n (%)
Dislike	n (%)	Unhelpful	n (%)	Difficult	n (%)	Little trust	n (%)
Like	n (%)	Helpful	n (%)	Easy	n (%)	Trust it	n (%)
Like a lot	n (%)	Very helpful	n (%)	Very easy	n (%)	Trust it very much	n (%)
Like or like a lot*	N (%)	Helpful or very helpful*	N (%)	Easy or very easy*	N (%)	Trust it or trust it very much	N (%)

* Missing values will be pooled with dislike a lot and dislike, very unhelpful and unhelpful, very difficult and difficult, or very little trust and little trust.

Table 7. Potential effect modifiers

Factor (comparison)	Interaction between intervention and factor
Outcome	
Version of the resources (projector vs blackboard)	
Passing score (> n out of 18 correct answers)	OR (95% CI) p-value
Mastery score (> n out of 18 correct answers)	OR (95% CI) p-value
Test score (% correct)	Difference in adjusted differences (95% CI) p-value
Class size (continuous variable)	
Passing score (> n out of 18 correct answers)	Slope (95% CI) p-value
Mastery score (> n out of 18 correct answers)	Slope (95% CI) p-value
Test score (% correct)	Slope (95% CI) p-value
Prior term examination scores (continuous variable)	
Passing score (> n out of 18 correct answers)	Slope (95% CI) p-value
Mastery score (> n out of 18 correct answers)	Slope (95% CI) p-value
Test score (% correct)	Slope (95% CI) p-value

Table 8: Subgroup analysis – English reading skills

	Control schools	Intervention schools	Adjusted difference	Odds ratio	ICC
Mean score, %					
Lacking basic reading skills (N=)	N children = Mean score: % (SD %)	N children = Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean difference: % (95% CI % to %)		n
Basic reading skills (N=)	N children = Mean score: % (SD %)	N children = Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean score: % (SD %)		n
Advanced reading skills (N=)	N children = Mean score: % (SD %)	N children = Mean score: % (SD %)	Mean difference: % (95% CI % to %)		n
Passing score (>n out of 18 correct answers)					
Lacking basic reading skills	N children = % of children N=	N children = 2224 % of children N=	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Basic reading skills	N children = % of children N=	N children = % of children N=	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Advanced reading skills	N children = % of children N=	N children = % of children N=	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Mastery score (≥ n out of 18 correct answers)					
Lacking basic reading skills	N children = % of children N=	N children = 2224 % of children N=	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Basic reading skills	N children = % of children N=	N children = % of children N=	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n
Advanced reading skills	N children = % of children N=	N children = % of children N=	% more children (95% CI % to %)	n (95% CI n to n)	n

9. PRISMA-P 2015 Checklist

Section/topic	#	Checklist item	Information reported		Page
			Yes	No	
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION					
Title					
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a systematic review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous systematic review, identify as such	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (e.g., PROSPERO) and registration number in the Abstract	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not yet registered
Authors					
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, and e-mail address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Contributions	3b	Describe contributions of protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable
Support					
Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
Sponsor	5b	Provide name for the review funder and/or sponsor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
Role of sponsor/funder	5c	Describe roles of funder(s), sponsor(s), and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
INTRODUCTION					
Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	5-6
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to participants, interventions, comparators, and outcomes (PICO)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	6-9
METHODS					

Section/topic	#	Checklist item	Information reported		Page
			Yes	No	
Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (e.g., PICO, study design, setting, time frame) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10-11
Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (e.g., electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers, or other grey literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable
STUDY RECORDS					
Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (e.g., two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (i.e., screening, eligibility, and inclusion in meta-analysis)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (e.g., piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (e.g., PICO items, funding sources), any pre-planned data assumptions and simplifications	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	15-21
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	15-19
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	Describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
DATA					
Synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be quantitatively synthesized	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	19-21
	15b	If data are appropriate for quantitative synthesis, describe planned summary measures, methods of handling data, and methods of combining data from studies, including any planned exploration of consistency (e.g., I^2 , Kendall's tau)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	19-21
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	20-21
	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable

Section/topic	#	Checklist item	Information reported		Page
			Yes	No	
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (e.g., publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (e.g., GRADE)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	22